

Table 5. Appendix 2 to “Spectral magnetic helicity of solar active regions” by Gosain & Brandenburg

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	11	15	18:35	3.4	1.9	1.9	2.9	101	0.26	4.35	-23.0	-20.5	113221	11897
2013	11	16	11:00	3.5	1.0	0.9	8.2	75	0.15	3.98	-23.0	-11.6	113224	11897
2013	11	16	19:00	3.2	0.3	0.3	6.4	50	0.05	3.78	-23.0	-7.2	113225	11897
2013	11	17	3:00	3.1	0.3	0.3	9.8	50	0.05	4.05	-23.0	-2.9	113226	11897
2013	11	17	10:00	3.0	0.5	0.4	9.0	64	0.07	4.42	-23.0	0.8	113227	11897
2013	11	17	20:01	2.8	0.5	0.5	8.2	53	0.07	4.54	-23.0	6.2	113231	11897
2013	11	18	4:10	2.1	-0.1	-0.1	3.3	27	-0.02	5.15	-23.0	10.6	113232	11897
2013	11	19	11:02	15.6	-12.4	-12.4	9.4	-154	-0.16	9.92	4.8	9.9	113237	11899
2013	11	19	14:00	15.5	-12.6	-12.6	2.9	-175	-0.16	9.93	4.8	11.4	113238	11899
2013	11	19	16:45	15.3	-12.3	-12.3	3.2	-170	-0.16	9.90	4.8	12.9	113239	11899
2013	11	19	20:00	15.3	-11.9	-11.9	0.1	-163	-0.16	9.90	4.8	14.7	113240	11899
2013	11	19	22:45	14.9	-11.3	-11.3	0.9	-167	-0.15	9.87	4.8	16.3	113241	11899
2013	11	20	5:00	14.9	-11.6	-11.6	0.3	-180	-0.16	9.80	4.8	19.7	113244	11899
2013	11	28	1:05	2.5	0.2	0.2	0.8	19	0.04	4.50	-11.3	-8.9	113275	11907
2013	11	29	13:00	2.5	0.3	0.3	3.1	14	0.04	5.34	-10.1	15.8	113278	11907
2013	12	1	23:05	1.6	0.2	0.2	7.6	75	0.07	4.24	-26.6	8.4	113283	11908
2013	12	2	10:06	1.2	0.1	0.1	-0.2	5	0.04	4.57	-26.6	14.1	113284	11908
2013	12	2	22:05	1.4	0.1	0.1	1.5	26	0.03	4.29	-26.6	20.5	113285	11908
2013	12	3	10:34	1.8	0.2	0.2	2.1	19	0.03	6.58	-20.4	2.7	113286	11909
2013	12	4	0:50	1.5	0.1	0.1	0.4	13	0.03	6.53	-20.4	10.4	113288	11909
2013	12	4	3:20	1.5	0.2	0.1	1.2	18	0.03	6.57	-20.4	11.8	113289	11909
2013	12	14	9:41	7.4	-1.0	-1.0	5.7	-2	-0.04	7.51	4.8	-19.6	113332	11921
2013	12	14	15:00	7.8	-1.4	-1.4	-0.2	-45	-0.05	7.63	4.8	-16.7	113333	11921
2013	12	14	20:00	8.0	-1.2	-1.2	3.8	-21	-0.04	7.54	4.8	-13.9	113334	11921
2013	12	15	2:00	8.0	-1.4	-1.4	1.4	-35	-0.05	7.51	4.8	-10.6	113335	11921
2013	12	15	6:42	8.0	-1.4	-1.4	-2.8	-45	-0.05	7.52	4.8	-7.9	113336	11921
2013	12	17	18:29	5.2	-0.8	-0.8	4.2	14	-0.05	6.81	6.6	25.1	113338	11921
2013	12	19	18:21	3.2	-0.2	-0.2	2.4	-39	-0.03	3.73	-16.2	12.2	113341	11928
2013	12	26	10:29	2.3	-0.7	-0.7	-0.1	1	-0.10	6.31	-17.7	2.5	113384	11934
2013	12	26	15:40	2.6	-0.8	-0.7	1.7	4	-0.10	6.06	-17.7	5.3	113385	11934
2013	12	26	20:30	2.5	-0.6	-0.6	1.2	3	-0.08	5.91	-17.7	8.0	113386	11934

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2013	12	31	10:16	5.6	-3.0	-2.9	3.5	-52	-0.17	6.13	-16.9	26.3	113416	11936
2013	12	31	12:00	5.7	-2.8	-2.8	2.1	-95	-0.16	6.06	-16.9	27.2	113417	11936
2013	12	31	14:00	5.7	-2.7	-2.6	4.0	-53	-0.15	6.05	-16.9	28.3	113418	11936
2014	1	5	18:25	18.9	27.6	27.5	23.0	606	0.32	9.05	-9.3	-26.4	113442	11944
2014	1	6	0:36	21.6	25.1	25.0	22.0	514	0.27	8.50	-9.3	-23.1	113443	11944
2014	1	6	5:35	22.0	26.4	26.2	15.4	498	0.27	8.91	-9.3	-20.7	113444	11944
2014	1	6	11:35	22.4	26.1	26.0	13.7	500	0.26	9.08	-9.3	-17.4	113445	11944
2014	1	6	20:50	22.5	28.8	28.7	21.5	545	0.27	9.49	-9.3	-12.3	113446	11944
2014	1	7	2:50	22.2	26.9	26.7	11.1	556	0.26	9.31	-9.3	-9.0	113447	11944
2014	1	7	15:13	15.4	18.9	18.6	42.6	819	0.31	7.98	-8.8	-3.3	113450	11944
2014	1	7	21:20	19.3	24.8	24.5	43.7	875	0.29	8.76	-8.8	0.1	113451	11944
2014	1	8	8:45	21.2	28.1	27.9	26.4	781	0.28	9.43	-8.8	6.4	113453	11944
2014	1	8	15:30	17.4	21.3	21.0	32.9	761	0.29	8.41	-8.8	10.1	113454	11944
2014	1	8	21:51	20.7	25.2	25.0	23.7	654	0.26	9.39	-8.8	13.7	113455	11944
2014	1	9	4:05	19.3	22.0	21.8	16.9	536	0.24	9.55	-8.8	17.1	113456	11944
2014	1	9	16:00	18.2	18.6	18.5	17.6	440	0.21	9.49	-8.8	23.7	113458	11944
2014	1	16	6:52	2.6	1.6	1.5	0.2	68	0.21	5.65	-17.2	20.1	113467	11949
2014	1	16	10:00	2.6	1.4	1.4	-0.5	59	0.20	5.54	-17.2	21.8	113468	11949
2014	1	16	13:00	2.4	1.3	1.3	0.4	55	0.19	5.51	-17.2	23.4	113469	11949
2014	1	16	17:00	2.2	1.2	1.2	3.5	65	0.20	5.42	-17.2	25.6	113470	11949
2014	1	16	22:00	2.0	1.1	1.1	0.5	56	0.20	5.38	-17.2	28.4	113471	11949
2014	2	1	10:42	17.8	-8.4	-8.5	5.5	253	-0.13	7.13	-13.8	-24.1	113526	11967
2014	2	1	14:00	18.7	-9.1	-9.2	14.4	303	-0.13	7.21	-13.8	-22.3	113527	11967
2014	2	1	16:54	18.4	-9.2	-9.3	16.5	327	-0.14	7.13	-13.8	-21.4	113528	11967
2014	2	1	20:13	18.8	-11.7	-11.7	9.7	231	-0.17	7.32	-13.8	-18.9	113529	11967
2014	2	1	23:19	19.6	-13.0	-13.0	7.7	137	-0.18	7.27	-13.8	-17.2	113530	11967
2014	2	2	2:20	19.7	-14.6	-14.6	17.5	125	-0.20	7.36	-13.8	-15.5	113531	11967
2014	2	2	4:15	20.1	-15.9	-16.0	23.5	216	-0.21	7.41	-13.8	-14.5	113532	11967
2014	2	2	7:12	20.6	-16.5	-16.5	21.3	177	-0.22	7.35	-13.8	-12.9	113533	11967
2014	2	2	10:20	21.0	-16.9	-17.0	16.4	204	-0.22	7.38	-13.8	-11.1	113534	11967
2014	2	2	13:00	14.0	-17.6	-17.6	29.8	-16	-0.37	6.71	-13.8	-9.7	113535	11967
2014	2	2	16:00	7.0	-2.3	-2.2	10.3	-93	-0.12	5.70	-13.8	-8.0	113536	11967
2014	2	2	19:20	8.3	-3.7	-3.6	15.1	-122	-0.15	5.87	-13.8	-6.2	113537	11967

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	2	2	22:30	18.5	-17.4	-17.5	46.0	251	-0.28	6.68	-13.8	-4.5	113538	11967
2014	2	3	1:30	23.4	-27.9	-27.8	13.6	-252	-0.31	7.62	-13.8	-2.8	113539	11967
2014	2	3	4:40	23.9	-27.4	-27.4	4.5	-358	-0.31	7.45	-13.8	-1.1	113540	11967
2014	2	3	7:50	18.1	-27.2	-27.2	40.2	15	-0.42	7.07	-13.8	0.7	113541	11967
2014	2	3	18:23	21.8	-26.2	-26.0	-5.9	-424	-0.30	8.01	-12.7	3.9	113545	11967
2014	2	4	0:38	22.6	-32.2	-32.0	5.3	-297	-0.35	8.18	-12.7	7.4	113547	11967
2014	2	4	3:40	22.3	-33.3	-33.2	-8.3	-314	-0.36	8.34	-12.7	9.4	113548	11967
2014	2	4	7:02	22.0	-31.3	-31.1	-17.0	-474	-0.35	7.98	-12.7	13.7	113549	11967
2014	2	4	10:00	15.9	-12.0	-11.9	18.7	-157	-0.22	6.68	-12.7	14.1	113550	11967
2014	2	4	19:00	20.9	-19.9	-19.6	-19.8	-552	-0.26	7.32	-12.7	20.7	113553	11967
2014	2	5	1:10	20.1	-19.9	-19.9	4.0	-277	-0.26	7.46	-12.7	24.1	113555	11967
2014	2	5	7:30	18.0	-13.5	-13.6	7.3	-115	-0.22	6.94	-12.7	27.1	113557	11967
2014	2	10	7:36	3.7	0.3	0.2	15.4	171	0.04	3.95	-11.9	-22.8	113572	11974
2014	2	13	10:31	7.9	-3.0	-2.9	15.3	-97	-0.13	5.84	-12.7	15.0	113595	11974
2014	2	13	14:30	11.3	1.9	1.8	7.1	239	0.07	4.73	-12.7	17.2	113596	11974
2014	2	13	19:31	11.5	2.3	2.0	2.1	237	0.07	5.29	-12.7	20.0	113598	11974
2014	2	14	0:00	12.2	1.7	1.5	5.7	275	0.05	5.53	-12.7	22.4	113599	11974
2014	2	14	3:08	8.3	-0.6	-0.7	13.9	254	-0.03	5.11	-12.7	24.0	113600	11974
2014	2	14	6:31	11.8	-0.5	-0.8	11.0	343	-0.02	5.19	-12.7	26.0	113601	11974
2014	3	1	2:28	3.4	-2.3	-2.3	1.8	-65	-0.27	5.15	-14.3	-24.1	113643	11990
2014	3	1	23:55	3.5	-3.2	-3.1	-0.4	-96	-0.34	5.37	-14.3	-12.4	113644	11990
2014	3	2	3:03	3.5	-3.3	-3.2	-1.2	-100	-0.34	5.33	-14.3	-10.6	113645	11990
2014	3	2	23:05	3.2	-3.2	-3.2	2.2	-59	-0.35	5.63	-14.3	0.4	113646	11990
2014	3	3	2:04	3.1	-2.9	-2.9	3.3	-51	-0.34	5.52	-14.3	2.0	113647	11990
2014	3	3	23:33	3.2	-2.2	-2.2	3.0	-39	-0.25	5.62	-14.3	13.8	113650	11990
2014	3	4	2:40	3.2	-2.2	-2.2	1.8	-39	-0.25	5.58	-14.3	15.5	113651	11990
2014	3	4	23:06	3.3	-2.6	-2.6	-0.2	-70	-0.28	5.64	-13.6	28.3	113653	11990
2014	3	11	23:30	4.4	-2.6	-2.5	1.5	-109	-0.20	5.82	-19.1	-25.4	113670	12002
2014	3	12	2:40	5.0	-3.1	-3.0	-4.2	-176	-0.23	5.44	-19.1	-23.7	113671	12002
2014	3	12	7:40	5.0	-2.5	-2.5	0.5	-114	-0.18	5.50	-19.1	-20.9	113672	12002
2014	3	12	11:00	4.9	-2.2	-2.1	-2.1	-124	-0.16	5.61	-19.1	-19.1	113673	12002
2014	3	12	13:30	4.8	-1.8	-1.8	-1.2	-93	-0.13	5.67	-19.1	-17.8	113674	12002
2014	4	2	14:05	0.8	0.0	0.0	1.7	1	0.00	2.91	17.3	-3.6	113757	12022

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	4	2	16:00	0.8	-0.0	-0.0	0.3	2	-0.01	2.81	17.3	-1.9	113758	12022
2014	4	2	17:40	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.8	4	0.00	2.81	17.3	-1.6	113759	12022
2014	4	4	8:31	3.5	-2.4	-2.4	-0.7	-60	-0.21	6.37	12.1	-28.1	113761	12027
2014	4	4	12:30	3.5	-2.5	-2.5	0.1	-41	-0.21	6.46	11.8	-19.6	113762	12027
2014	4	4	15:30	3.7	-2.4	-2.4	-1.6	-47	-0.20	6.39	11.8	-17.4	113763	12027
2014	4	5	12:00	3.9	-2.8	-2.8	1.5	-63	-0.21	6.62	12.1	-13.0	113764	12027
2014	4	5	13:00	4.0	-2.5	-2.5	3.1	-43	-0.20	6.38	12.1	-12.3	113765	12027
2014	4	6	11:07	3.9	-1.9	-1.9	3.0	-25	-0.16	6.11	12.1	-0.1	113766	12027
2014	4	6	13:00	4.1	-1.9	-1.9	3.0	-30	-0.15	5.99	12.1	0.9	113767	12027
2014	4	8	11:07	3.3	-1.2	-1.2	1.1	-38	-0.13	5.61	12.1	26.4	113768	12027
2014	4	8	13:07	3.3	-1.4	-1.4	1.1	-53	-0.15	5.65	12.1	27.6	113769	12027
2014	4	13	14:12	3.4	0.1	0.1	0.3	-7	0.01	6.10	12.7	-7.8	113780	12032
2014	4	15	9:56	5.0	3.6	3.6	-0.3	134	0.24	5.97	-17.0	-8.0	113781	12036
2014	4	16	14:05	5.3	3.6	3.6	16.4	195	0.24	5.65	-17.7	9.0	113804	12036
2014	4	16	17:05	5.7	4.5	4.4	22.8	274	0.27	5.82	-17.8	7.7	113805	12036
2014	4	18	12:34	3.2	1.5	1.5	6.3	122	0.19	4.87	-18.3	19.5	113812	12036
2014	4	20	2:10	2.9	1.2	1.2	4.7	70	0.18	4.71	-20.0	25.2	113819	12036
2014	4	23	7:02	2.8	0.4	0.4	2.5	22	0.05	5.99	18.2	10.6	113828	12042
2014	4	23	8:50	2.8	0.3	0.3	1.9	14	0.04	5.98	18.4	17.0	113829	12042
2014	4	24	6:15	2.9	0.4	0.5	-0.5	-7	0.05	5.63	18.4	28.7	113830	12042
2014	5	10	10:55	5.3	-6.7	-6.7	1.7	-159	-0.41	6.17	3.4	-24.4	113864	12056
2014	5	10	14:14	6.5	-2.4	-2.3	4.7	-73	-0.13	5.65	3.4	-22.6	113865	12056
2014	5	11	16:40	6.7	-1.7	-1.6	5.8	-74	-0.10	5.09	3.4	-7.9	113870	12056
2014	5	12	2:15	5.5	-0.7	-0.7	1.0	-30	-0.05	5.14	3.4	-2.6	113871	12056
2014	5	13	14:29	3.7	-1.9	-1.9	-2.0	-51	-0.20	5.07	4.6	13.1	113874	12056
2014	5	15	17:27	3.0	-0.7	-0.6	5.0	2	-0.10	4.46	2.4	24.6	113881	12056
2014	5	15	20:40	3.1	-0.5	-0.5	0.6	-10	-0.08	4.29	2.3	24.1	113882	12056
2014	6	1	11:30	0.6	-0.0	-0.0	-1.6	-1	-0.03	3.40	-10.9	18.6	113974	12078
2014	6	7	14:53	4.8	-2.6	-2.6	-1.9	-12	-0.18	6.14	-13.2	-9.6	114018	12080
2014	6	7	19:54	5.8	-2.9	-2.9	-0.9	17	-0.15	6.37	-13.2	-8.7	114019	12080
2014	6	7	23:15	5.7	-1.8	-1.9	-10.2	6	-0.10	6.30	-13.2	-7.2	114020	12080
2014	6	8	2:23	5.1	-2.5	-2.6	-1.4	34	-0.15	6.60	-13.2	-5.1	114021	12080
2014	6	8	13:51	5.1	-2.7	-2.7	-3.4	-31	-0.16	6.75	-13.2	1.2	114025	12080

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	6	8	18:53	5.2	-2.0	-2.0	2.6	32	-0.12	6.72	-13.2	4.0	114026	12080
2014	6	8	23:40	5.5	-2.0	-2.1	0.1	83	-0.11	6.62	-13.2	6.6	114027	12080
2014	6	9	4:35	6.1	-0.7	-0.9	10.4	214	-0.04	5.93	-13.2	8.8	114028	12080
2014	6	9	9:34	6.0	-1.8	-1.9	9.4	102	-0.09	6.65	-13.2	9.1	114029	12080
2014	6	9	14:26	6.6	-2.0	-2.1	16.4	136	-0.08	6.97	-13.2	12.2	114030	12080
2014	6	9	19:21	7.5	-1.7	-1.8	14.3	147	-0.06	7.15	-15.1	17.7	114031	12080
2014	6	10	0:16	7.4	-2.3	-2.4	4.8	41	-0.08	7.67	-15.1	20.4	114032	12080
2014	6	10	3:33	7.2	-3.0	-3.1	3.1	64	-0.10	7.99	-15.1	22.2	114033	12080
2014	6	10	11:45	7.1	-2.6	-2.7	5.2	70	-0.09	8.16	-15.0	13.6	114035	12080
2014	6	10	15:02	7.1	-3.1	-3.2	-0.7	57	-0.10	8.14	-15.1	28.5	114036	12080
2014	6	10	16:41	7.1	-3.0	-3.0	0.6	39	-0.10	8.09	-15.0	15.7	114037	12080
2014	6	10	23:15	6.4	-2.5	-2.6	5.6	80	-0.10	8.05	-15.0	16.3	114038	12080
2014	6	11	7:27	6.1	-1.9	-2.1	7.3	149	-0.08	7.93	-15.0	20.8	114040	12080
2014	6	11	9:08	6.1	-2.1	-2.2	6.4	110	-0.09	7.98	-15.0	21.5	114041	12080
2014	6	11	12:22	5.9	-2.0	-2.1	3.4	71	-0.09	8.00	-14.9	22.0	114042	12080
2014	6	11	15:39	5.7	-1.8	-1.9	5.3	82	-0.08	8.03	-14.9	24.6	114043	12080
2014	6	14	10:54	4.3	2.9	2.8	7.0	179	0.29	4.63	-20.9	-21.1	114054	12087
2014	6	14	16:00	4.2	2.8	2.7	6.4	175	0.27	4.82	-20.9	-13.1	114055	12087
2014	6	14	20:48	3.6	2.1	2.0	7.7	136	0.24	4.68	-20.9	-10.9	114056	12087
2014	6	15	3:19	3.6	2.0	2.0	9.3	128	0.23	4.82	-20.9	-16.8	114057	12087
2014	6	15	8:14	3.5	2.0	2.0	2.0	104	0.23	5.01	-20.9	-12.2	114058	12087
2014	6	15	14:48	3.3	1.9	1.9	6.3	110	0.24	4.88	-20.9	-11.2	114059	12087
2014	6	15	21:22	3.1	1.4	1.4	6.2	95	0.20	4.72	-20.9	-7.7	114060	12087
2014	6	16	0:40	3.2	1.5	1.4	3.5	84	0.19	4.79	-20.9	-5.9	114062	12087
2014	6	16	3:55	3.2	1.4	1.4	7.6	94	0.18	4.75	-20.9	-4.1	114063	12087
2014	6	16	8:51	3.1	1.3	1.3	5.2	70	0.17	4.80	-20.9	-1.4	114064	12087
2014	6	16	13:46	3.0	1.5	1.5	6.6	62	0.20	4.94	-20.9	1.2	114065	12087
2014	6	16	20:20	3.3	2.0	1.9	5.4	85	0.23	5.21	-20.9	4.8	114066	12087
2014	6	16	23:37	3.7	1.9	1.9	-0.7	44	0.21	4.98	-20.9	6.6	114067	12087
2014	6	17	2:53	3.8	2.2	2.1	2.8	105	0.22	5.37	-20.9	4.6	114068	12087
2014	6	17	7:49	3.6	2.2	2.2	6.1	113	0.23	5.30	-20.9	11.0	114069	12087
2014	6	17	12:44	3.6	2.0	2.0	4.8	109	0.22	5.24	-20.9	13.7	114070	12087
2014	6	17	16:01	3.6	2.1	2.0	4.5	116	0.22	5.13	-20.9	15.4	114071	12087

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	6	17	22:35	3.4	1.6	1.5	3.9	103	0.19	5.07	-20.9	10.0	114072	12087
2014	6	18	3:30	3.2	1.2	1.1	2.6	59	0.15	4.83	-20.9	15.3	114073	12087
2014	6	18	8:25	3.2	1.4	1.3	0.1	47	0.18	4.76	-20.9	24.3	114074	12087
2014	6	18	11:42	2.9	1.3	1.2	1.5	53	0.18	4.66	-20.8	13.3	114075	12087
2014	6	18	14:59	2.8	1.1	1.0	-0.2	45	0.16	4.67	-20.8	14.5	114076	12087
2014	6	18	21:33	2.4	0.7	0.7	-0.5	28	0.13	4.74	-20.8	18.7	114077	12087
2014	6	19	20:31	1.7	0.4	0.4	-0.5	20	0.10	4.58	-20.6	24.0	114081	12087
2014	6	21	20:29	1.3	-0.7	-0.7	-2.0	-36	-0.28	3.84	-11.6	4.9	114089	12093
2014	6	21	22:08	1.2	-0.7	-0.7	-2.1	-38	-0.30	3.95	-11.6	5.8	114090	12093
2014	6	21	23:46	1.2	-0.7	-0.7	-1.6	-30	-0.29	3.82	-11.6	6.7	114091	12093
2014	6	22	1:24	1.2	-0.7	-0.6	-1.8	-39	-0.29	3.80	-11.6	7.6	114092	12093
2014	6	28	10:06	1.6	0.1	0.1	1.0	11	0.04	4.26	6.2	1.3	114144	12096
2014	6	28	11:15	1.6	0.1	0.1	1.0	14	0.04	4.21	6.2	2.5	114145	12096
2014	6	28	12:51	1.6	0.2	0.2	2.4	15	0.05	4.13	6.2	3.4	114146	12096
2014	6	28	14:31	1.7	0.2	0.2	2.3	3	0.05	4.15	6.2	4.3	114147	12096
2014	6	28	16:20	1.6	0.2	0.2	-0.0	3	0.05	4.17	6.2	5.3	114148	12096
2014	6	28	18:12	1.5	0.1	0.2	4.1	14	0.05	4.13	6.2	6.3	114149	12096
2014	6	28	19:33	1.6	0.2	0.2	4.3	22	0.07	4.19	6.2	7.1	114150	12096
2014	6	28	21:11	1.6	0.1	0.1	3.9	20	0.03	4.17	6.2	8.0	114151	12096
2014	6	28	22:46	1.5	0.0	0.0	4.7	17	0.01	4.28	6.2	8.5	114152	12096
2014	6	29	0:21	1.4	0.1	0.1	3.6	24	0.02	4.15	6.2	9.8	114153	12096
2014	6	29	3:38	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	1.8	3	-0.03	4.15	6.2	10.1	114154	12096
2014	6	29	5:16	1.4	-0.1	-0.1	-0.5	1	-0.02	4.36	6.2	11.0	114155	12096
2014	6	29	5:58	1.3	0.1	0.1	1.5	5	0.02	4.64	6.2	5.9	114156	12096
2014	6	29	8:34	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	0.4	-4	-0.07	4.19	6.2	14.3	114157	12096
2014	6	29	11:50	1.4	-0.2	-0.3	3.7	7	-0.08	4.26	6.2	16.2	114158	12096
2014	6	29	15:09	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	-1.0	5	-0.07	4.04	6.2	13.6	114159	12096
2014	6	29	18:32	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.7	-3	-0.08	4.08	6.2	19.9	114160	12096
2014	6	29	23:19	1.2	-0.3	-0.3	1.1	0	-0.12	4.08	6.2	22.5	114161	12096
2014	6	30	4:14	1.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	0	-0.10	3.96	6.2	25.3	114162	12096
2014	6	30	9:09	1.0	-0.3	-0.2	-0.4	-10	-0.13	3.92	6.4	17.3	114163	12096
2014	7	3	19:11	10.1	13.4	13.3	9.2	330	0.37	7.22	-13.7	-16.4	114194	12104
2014	7	3	22:27	10.0	12.9	12.7	16.6	327	0.36	7.23	-13.7	-14.6	114195	12104

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	7	4	2:00	9.6	12.6	12.5	15.8	301	0.36	7.29	-13.7	-12.7	114196	12104
2014	7	4	3:22	9.6	12.5	12.4	18.1	310	0.36	7.26	-13.7	-11.9	114197	12104
2014	7	4	6:40	9.4	12.6	12.4	14.1	327	0.37	7.29	-12.6	-6.5	114198	12104
2014	7	4	13:13	8.9	11.6	11.5	11.5	320	0.35	7.37	-13.7	-6.5	114205	12104
2014	7	4	18:33	8.7	11.1	11.0	11.6	273	0.34	7.36	-13.7	-3.6	114209	12104
2014	7	5	2:23	8.2	9.8	9.7	12.8	238	0.33	7.19	-13.7	0.7	114211	12104
2014	7	5	12:11	7.6	8.6	8.6	9.3	230	0.32	7.03	-13.8	6.2	114213	12104
2014	7	5	13:50	7.3	7.8	7.8	12.6	239	0.31	6.97	-13.9	8.5	114214	12104
2014	7	5	22:20	6.6	6.8	6.8	3.5	156	0.29	7.06	-13.9	13.1	114216	12104
2014	7	6	1:19	6.3	6.5	6.5	4.4	142	0.29	7.12	-13.9	14.8	114218	12104
2014	7	6	4:35	6.1	6.7	6.6	8.0	154	0.30	7.14	-13.9	16.6	114219	12104
2014	7	6	21:10	5.1	6.0	6.0	2.0	133	0.34	6.97	-13.9	25.7	114224	12104
2014	7	7	1:55	4.8	5.4	5.4	-0.7	109	0.33	6.87	-13.6	18.4	114226	12104
2014	7	9	6:37	13.8	-3.0	-3.0	6.2	154	-0.05	8.29	-10.3	7.1	114248	12109
2014	7	9	9:55	14.8	-5.0	-5.0	8.9	53	-0.08	8.77	-10.2	8.2	114249	12109
2014	7	9	13:20	14.4	-4.6	-4.6	10.6	66	-0.07	8.80	-10.3	10.8	114250	12109
2014	7	9	16:30	14.3	-5.3	-5.3	2.2	29	-0.08	8.81	-10.3	12.6	114251	12109
2014	7	9	19:50	14.0	-5.2	-5.2	1.1	-20	-0.08	8.79	-10.3	14.4	114252	12109
2014	7	9	23:10	13.8	-5.2	-5.1	6.7	15	-0.08	8.75	-10.3	16.2	114253	12109
2014	7	10	2:30	13.4	-5.0	-4.9	6.9	36	-0.08	8.78	-10.3	18.1	114254	12109
2014	7	10	17:05	1.2	0.3	0.3	-2.0	20	0.12	3.72	6.6	-27.6	114257	12113
2014	7	10	20:30	1.1	0.2	0.2	-0.3	22	0.09	3.61	6.6	-25.7	114258	12113
2014	7	11	1:03	1.2	0.3	0.3	-1.5	24	0.16	3.54	6.6	-23.1	114260	12113
2014	7	11	4:20	1.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	25	0.17	3.51	6.6	-21.3	114261	12113
2014	7	11	7:37	1.2	0.4	0.4	-1.2	32	0.19	3.46	6.6	-19.5	114262	12113
2014	7	11	22:31	1.3	0.5	0.4	2.6	43	0.18	3.92	6.6	-11.2	114266	12113
2014	7	12	1:40	1.3	0.4	0.4	3.1	34	0.16	3.91	6.6	-9.4	114268	12113
2014	7	12	4:56	1.4	0.5	0.5	4.7	52	0.20	3.86	6.6	-7.6	114269	12113
2014	7	12	8:13	1.4	0.6	0.6	1.0	21	0.22	3.91	6.6	-5.8	114270	12113
2014	7	13	12:07	1.5	0.6	0.6	4.8	39	0.19	4.06	6.6	9.7	114271	12113
2014	7	30	6:15	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.8	4	-0.07	4.29	-15.4	-18.5	114317	12125
2014	7	30	7:50	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	1.4	12	-0.07	4.40	-15.4	-14.9	114318	12125
2014	7	30	9:35	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	0.7	3	-0.08	4.35	-16.0	-29.4	114319	12125

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	8	2	14:30	2.2	0.9	0.9	7.1	90	0.20	4.41	-9.5	-12.6	114338	12130
2014	8	6	8:33	1.7	-0.2	-0.1	3.0	-31	-0.05	3.50	-20.2	10.1	114366	12132
2014	8	7	21:00	1.8	0.4	0.3	0.5	24	0.09	4.58	-21.1	17.9	114375	12132
2014	8	7	22:30	1.8	0.3	0.3	3.1	34	0.08	4.60	-21.6	30.1	114376	12132
2014	8	8	3:30	1.6	0.5	0.4	6.6	66	0.13	4.56	-20.8	16.6	114379	12132
2014	8	8	21:40	1.3	0.3	0.3	3.1	45	0.11	4.81	-20.3	23.0	114390	12132
2014	8	9	15:14	2.6	-0.0	-0.0	2.7	5	-0.01	6.15	12.2	-27.0	114393	12135
2014	8	16	9:48	3.3	-0.4	-0.5	7.6	101	-0.05	4.50	12.7	-7.2	114414	12139
2014	8	16	15:15	3.4	-0.6	-0.6	5.1	15	-0.07	4.76	12.6	-9.7	114415	12139
2014	8	17	0:15	3.0	-0.1	-0.2	7.3	44	-0.02	4.33	12.6	-5.3	114416	12139
2014	8	17	10:15	3.1	-0.1	-0.1	2.7	42	-0.02	4.34	12.6	0.2	114417	12139
2014	8	17	20:15	2.6	-0.2	-0.2	5.4	11	-0.04	4.27	12.6	4.8	114418	12139
2014	8	18	6:15	2.5	-0.1	-0.1	5.7	24	-0.02	4.18	12.6	11.3	114419	12139
2014	8	18	17:00	2.1	-0.1	-0.1	1.6	3	-0.01	4.15	12.6	17.2	114420	12139
2014	8	18	19:30	2.0	-0.1	-0.1	1.1	7	-0.01	4.23	12.6	18.6	114421	12139
2014	8	23	17:27	4.3	-2.5	-2.5	0.4	-47	-0.17	6.48	9.4	10.6	114457	12146
2014	8	24	18:06	4.0	-3.0	-3.0	3.6	-60	-0.23	6.47	9.4	24.2	114461	12146
2014	9	2	10:32	5.2	0.8	0.8	17.6	63	0.06	4.83	-16.8	3.4	114489	12152
2014	9	2	14:00	4.4	0.8	0.7	11.8	87	0.07	4.94	-16.8	5.2	114490	12152
2014	9	2	17:00	4.4	0.5	0.5	13.8	119	0.04	5.17	-16.8	6.9	114491	12152
2014	9	2	20:30	4.6	0.4	0.4	18.6	178	0.04	5.26	-16.8	8.8	114492	12152
2014	9	11	10:47	10.0	-17.5	-17.4	-7.6	-333	-0.45	7.66	14.1	2.7	114520	12158
2014	9	11	16:00	9.9	-16.4	-16.3	-10.1	-346	-0.43	7.62	14.1	5.5	114521	12158
2014	9	11	19:07	9.9	-16.4	-16.3	-7.6	-351	-0.43	7.62	14.1	7.3	114522	12158
2014	9	12	0:00	9.3	-15.5	-15.5	-10.9	-309	-0.44	7.48	14.1	10.0	114523	12158
2014	9	12	8:00	8.3	-13.2	-13.1	-11.0	-299	-0.42	7.43	14.1	14.4	114524	12158
2014	9	12	18:21	7.7	-10.9	-10.8	-12.3	-278	-0.39	7.20	14.1	18.2	114526	12158
2014	9	13	2:00	7.0	-9.2	-9.2	-9.1	-200	-0.38	7.04	14.4	16.0	114527	12158
2014	9	13	6:46	6.6	-8.5	-8.4	-7.1	-176	-0.37	6.94	14.1	27.0	114528	12158
2014	9	13	10:21	6.3	-8.1	-8.1	-7.8	-170	-0.37	6.97	14.1	28.9	114529	12158
2014	9	13	13:00	5.9	-7.2	-7.2	-8.1	-151	-0.36	6.87	14.6	19.7	114530	12158
2014	9	14	8:00	4.9	-5.5	-5.5	-7.6	-137	-0.34	6.74	15.1	23.2	114533	12158
2014	9	16	10:31	1.8	0.0	0.0	-0.0	6	0.00	4.84	11.6	-14.7	114540	12166

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	9	22	0:02	1.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.5	-4	-0.07	3.56	4.0	-15.7	114559	12169
2014	9	22	11:15	1.2	-0.2	-0.2	0.5	-8	-0.10	3.59	4.0	-9.4	114561	12169
2014	9	22	16:00	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	1.7	0	-0.10	3.53	4.0	-3.9	114562	12169
2014	9	22	23:04	1.4	-0.1	-0.1	2.3	3	-0.05	3.76	4.0	-2.9	114563	12169
2014	9	25	8:00	5.9	2.6	2.6	1.7	17	0.14	6.45	-12.4	-12.8	114590	12172
2014	9	25	11:03	6.7	4.8	4.6	41.6	480	0.28	5.00	-11.4	-19.3	114591	12172
2014	9	25	14:22	7.5	3.5	3.5	-2.4	23	0.15	6.27	-11.4	-17.4	114592	12172
2014	9	25	18:18	6.8	1.7	1.8	10.4	93	0.08	6.34	-11.4	-15.3	114593	12172
2014	9	25	23:00	7.2	2.5	2.4	0.3	74	0.11	6.45	-11.4	-12.7	114594	12172
2014	9	26	3:13	6.0	1.4	1.4	7.1	60	0.07	6.34	-11.4	-10.4	114595	12172
2014	9	26	8:05	6.8	0.6	0.6	3.3	-26	0.03	6.33	-11.4	-7.7	114596	12172
2014	9	26	12:00	6.3	0.9	0.9	6.8	36	0.05	6.06	-11.4	-5.5	114597	12172
2014	9	26	17:00	7.3	1.0	1.0	5.5	40	0.04	6.46	-11.4	-2.8	114598	12172
2014	9	26	22:00	6.2	-0.3	-0.3	6.7	45	-0.02	5.85	-11.4	-0.0	114599	12172
2014	9	27	4:00	7.0	1.6	1.5	8.5	41	0.07	6.61	-11.4	3.1	114600	12172
2014	9	27	11:00	6.5	-2.4	-2.4	6.4	-56	-0.13	5.84	-11.4	7.2	114601	12172
2014	9	27	16:00	6.5	1.7	1.8	13.8	45	0.08	6.62	-11.4	7.6	114602	12172
2014	9	27	20:50	6.4	-3.3	-3.2	-11.8	-154	-0.17	5.92	-11.4	11.2	114603	12172
2014	9	28	1:15	5.9	1.9	1.9	8.9	52	0.10	6.65	-11.4	13.4	114604	12172
2014	9	28	13:40	6.9	-7.8	-7.8	1.2	-116	-0.32	7.03	-11.4	21.9	114605	12172
2014	9	28	18:15	4.8	1.0	1.0	3.3	34	0.06	6.41	-11.4	24.4	114606	12172
2014	9	28	23:00	6.8	-7.5	-7.5	1.8	-159	-0.32	6.82	-11.4	27.0	114607	12172
2014	9	30	22:30	3.6	-0.4	-0.4	-3.7	-35	-0.04	5.45	11.6	-19.2	114611	12177
2014	10	1	4:45	3.7	0.0	-0.0	-4.3	-10	0.00	4.92	11.6	-15.8	114612	12177
2014	10	1	12:00	3.5	-0.2	-0.2	-1.2	-1	-0.02	5.05	11.6	-11.8	114613	12177
2014	10	1	18:25	3.0	-0.2	-0.2	5.0	31	-0.03	5.38	11.6	-8.2	114614	12177
2014	10	2	6:55	2.4	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-2	-0.05	5.19	11.6	-1.3	114615	12177
2014	10	2	10:22	4.5	0.4	0.3	4.0	72	0.03	6.02	-1.9	-15.7	114616	12178
2014	10	2	14:00	4.6	0.3	0.2	2.7	69	0.02	5.87	-1.9	-13.7	114617	12178
2014	10	3	7:56	4.4	0.5	0.5	3.1	14	0.04	5.90	-1.9	-3.3	114619	12178
2014	10	3	10:40	4.2	0.2	0.2	-0.2	17	0.02	5.82	-1.9	-2.2	114620	12178
2014	10	3	14:30	4.1	0.2	0.2	0.8	9	0.01	5.79	-1.9	-0.1	114621	12178
2014	10	3	21:00	4.0	0.2	0.2	-2.3	4	0.02	5.71	-1.9	3.5	114622	12178

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	10	7	16:55	0.8	0.1	0.1	0.2	3	0.02	4.91	0.3	26.1	114626	12178
2014	10	21	13:01	40.1	-35.6	-35.8	-15.3	-280	-0.19	9.42	-14.3	-14.9	114677	12192
2014	10	21	15:40	38.4	-37.3	-37.4	7.2	-164	-0.20	9.45	-14.8	-26.9	114678	12192
2014	10	21	19:00	37.3	-39.5	-39.5	4.8	-194	-0.22	9.71	-14.8	-25.1	114679	12192
2014	10	21	22:00	36.2	-40.2	-40.2	-15.7	-326	-0.23	9.77	-14.8	-23.5	114680	12192
2014	10	24	0:31	32.7	-42.4	-42.4	-7.9	-587	-0.27	9.70	-14.8	4.3	114683	12192
2014	10	24	2:10	32.7	-43.0	-43.0	6.6	-577	-0.27	9.70	-14.8	5.2	114684	12192
2014	10	24	4:00	20.6	2.2	2.3	29.5	75	0.03	8.04	-14.8	6.2	114685	12192
2014	10	24	7:00	31.4	-43.5	-43.5	-5.5	-599	-0.27	10.30	-14.8	7.8	114686	12192
2014	10	24	8:45	31.0	-42.1	-42.0	-3.9	-529	-0.26	10.27	-14.7	6.8	114687	12192
2014	10	24	23:41	28.3	-40.0	-39.9	-15.3	-771	-0.30	9.30	-14.6	11.6	114693	12192
2014	10	25	7:40	30.9	-44.1	-44.0	-2.4	-511	-0.28	10.14	-14.8	21.4	114694	12192
2014	11	2	6:18	0.8	-0.5	-0.5	-1.4	-36	-0.32	4.01	11.9	14.2	114711	12202
2014	11	5	11:01	3.6	2.4	2.2	2.0	251	0.30	4.48	15.8	-28.5	114724	12205
2014	11	6	6:28	5.9	5.8	5.3	7.6	511	0.40	4.88	15.2	-26.8	114735	12205
2014	11	10	7:57	5.2	2.9	2.6	5.1	251	0.22	5.13	15.0	-2.4	114759	12205
2014	11	10	12:34	3.2	2.2	2.0	8.9	211	0.36	3.88	15.1	0.0	114760	12205
2014	11	10	22:46	4.8	2.2	2.2	9.5	121	0.18	5.21	15.1	5.8	114761	12205
2014	11	11	18:38	4.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.5	-14	-0.02	5.43	15.1	17.2	114765	12205
2014	11	16	23:00	13.6	-1.6	-1.7	2.0	33	-0.03	7.54	-14.8	-28.3	114785	12209
2014	11	17	9:00	3.9	0.6	0.6	3.4	60	0.05	6.32	-14.9	-23.1	114786	12209
2014	11	18	12:00	14.3	2.9	2.9	2.0	104	0.05	8.72	-15.9	-14.8	114787	12209
2014	11	18	13:30	14.1	3.3	3.2	3.2	136	0.05	8.59	-15.9	-14.6	114788	12209
2014	11	18	16:05	13.7	4.2	4.1	4.4	160	0.07	8.42	-16.0	-18.5	114789	12209
2014	11	18	19:30	14.5	4.8	4.7	5.7	188	0.08	8.58	-16.1	-20.5	114790	12209
2014	11	18	22:40	14.7	4.7	4.6	5.4	184	0.07	8.73	-15.9	-9.7	114791	12209
2014	11	19	1:30	14.8	5.0	5.0	7.4	183	0.08	8.67	-16.1	-17.2	114792	12209
2014	11	19	3:15	14.8	5.3	5.3	8.1	207	0.08	8.60	-16.1	-16.2	114793	12209
2014	11	19	10:00	15.1	5.6	5.5	5.4	223	0.09	8.57	-16.1	-12.5	114794	12209
2014	11	19	13:00	14.9	6.3	6.2	10.9	353	0.10	8.43	-16.0	-10.9	114795	12209
2014	11	19	16:45	14.9	6.4	6.3	12.8	347	0.10	8.40	-16.0	-8.8	114796	12209
2014	11	19	20:00	14.4	6.5	6.4	14.6	358	0.11	8.41	-16.0	-6.0	114797	12209
2014	11	19	23:10	14.1	6.9	6.9	8.8	341	0.12	8.46	-16.0	-5.3	114798	12209

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	11	20	2:10	13.4	6.7	6.6	12.3	333	0.12	8.51	-16.1	-3.7	114799	12209
2014	11	20	7:00	13.1	6.2	6.2	8.6	305	0.11	8.44	-16.1	-1.1	114800	12209
2014	11	20	12:00	12.1	5.0	5.0	7.8	268	0.10	8.50	-16.0	1.7	114801	12209
2014	11	20	14:00	12.2	5.4	5.4	16.4	296	0.10	8.54	-16.1	2.8	114802	12209
2014	11	20	19:59	11.7	5.0	4.9	10.1	287	0.10	8.65	-16.1	6.0	114804	12209
2014	11	20	22:11	11.4	5.1	5.0	11.9	288	0.10	8.53	-16.1	7.3	114805	12209
2014	11	21	1:10	11.2	5.1	5.0	8.7	270	0.11	8.58	-16.1	8.9	114806	12209
2014	11	21	4:45	10.9	4.9	4.8	14.1	278	0.10	8.57	-16.1	10.8	114807	12209
2014	11	21	9:19	10.6	4.3	4.2	9.2	304	0.10	8.34	-16.0	6.9	114808	12209
2014	11	21	12:18	10.7	3.9	3.8	8.2	269	0.09	8.28	-16.1	15.0	114809	12209
2014	11	21	21:10	10.0	3.2	3.1	3.8	226	0.08	8.20	-15.9	11.1	114810	12209
2014	11	22	0:15	10.2	2.9	2.8	8.6	260	0.07	7.98	-15.9	13.1	114811	12209
2014	11	22	0:56	9.9	2.6	2.5	4.4	260	0.07	8.09	-16.1	21.8	114812	12209
2014	11	22	3:38	9.7	2.7	2.6	3.5	270	0.07	7.95	-16.1	23.3	114813	12209
2014	11	22	22:00	7.8	1.5	1.4	7.0	284	0.05	7.30	-15.8	19.3	114816	12209
2014	11	23	16:00	6.8	1.3	1.2	-1.2	151	0.05	7.11	-15.7	25.1	114821	12209
2014	11	27	10:20	2.2	0.1	0.1	0.3	24	0.02	4.60	-19.6	-27.1	114853	12217
2014	11	27	12:20	2.2	0.1	0.1	3.2	21	0.01	4.58	-19.6	-26.0	114854	12217
2014	11	29	19:40	9.7	0.4	0.3	5.4	83	0.01	7.23	-19.9	-16.9	114870	12222
2014	12	2	18:15	8.3	-2.2	-2.2	-2.6	-2	-0.07	7.74	-20.4	2.6	114880	12222
2014	12	2	21:15	8.2	-2.2	-2.3	-0.5	24	-0.07	7.88	-20.4	5.6	114881	12222
2014	12	3	0:15	4.0	0.3	0.3	-4.2	-59	0.02	5.96	-20.4	7.2	114882	12222
2014	12	3	8:15	7.3	-1.6	-1.6	-3.5	13	-0.05	8.05	-20.4	11.5	114883	12222
2014	12	3	11:10	3.6	1.0	1.0	0.1	33	0.10	5.57	-20.4	13.1	114884	12222
2014	12	3	14:00	7.0	-2.6	-2.6	-4.8	-21	-0.09	8.29	-20.4	14.6	114885	12222
2014	12	4	1:00	3.3	1.6	1.5	2.5	68	0.18	5.06	-20.4	14.0	114886	12222
2014	12	4	4:00	6.4	-2.8	-2.8	3.6	39	-0.10	8.36	-20.4	13.3	114887	12222
2014	12	4	7:15	2.8	1.2	1.1	1.1	52	0.17	4.97	-20.4	18.0	114888	12222
2014	12	4	14:15	5.6	-2.3	-2.3	3.7	1	-0.10	8.37	-20.4	28.6	114891	12222
2014	12	5	16:34	4.0	-3.4	-3.4	-0.5	-55	-0.20	8.42	-20.3	22.6	114903	12222
2014	12	9	14:05	2.7	0.4	0.3	4.2	20	0.05	5.15	-4.5	8.7	114912	12227
2014	12	9	22:02	2.8	0.2	0.2	1.6	34	0.03	5.05	-4.5	13.1	114913	12227
2014	12	10	7:28	2.8	0.2	0.2	1.8	42	0.03	4.95	-4.5	10.8	114915	12227

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2014	12	10	19:24	2.7	0.2	0.2	-0.6	30	0.04	5.10	-4.5	13.9	114918	12227
2014	12	11	21:37	2.2	-1.6	-1.6	2.8	-30	-0.27	5.32	-14.0	0.3	114921	12230
2014	12	12	10:15	5.0	-2.9	-2.8	-2.4	-55	-0.16	6.95	-14.0	7.5	114924	12230
2014	12	13	15:01	3.2	-0.8	-0.8	1.5	24	-0.08	6.09	-13.5	26.9	114929	12230
2014	12	15	11:00	2.1	-0.7	-0.7	0.7	-10	-0.11	6.06	-13.7	27.1	114940	12230
2014	12	16	11:05	10.8	15.1	14.9	-1.3	385	0.43	6.42	-19.0	-12.6	114944	12242
2014	12	16	23:00	12.6	20.0	19.8	2.5	410	0.46	6.81	-18.9	-13.3	114945	12242
2014	12	17	1:01	10.0	17.0	16.8	27.2	457	0.48	7.05	-18.9	-9.4	114947	12242
2014	12	17	10:01	10.6	21.0	20.9	13.9	504	0.54	7.27	-19.0	-7.9	114949	12242
2014	12	17	23:31	13.1	22.5	22.4	22.6	600	0.46	7.38	-19.0	0.0	114951	12242
2014	12	18	15:13	13.3	18.6	18.4	17.9	597	0.37	7.44	-18.9	10.6	114953	12242
2014	12	18	22:30	11.8	16.8	16.3	36.8	752	0.39	7.18	-19.0	12.0	114954	12242
2014	12	19	10:00	11.9	17.8	17.5	23.5	615	0.40	7.38	-19.0	12.5	114955	12242
2014	12	19	15:00	10.9	14.7	14.4	21.6	628	0.38	7.01	-19.0	21.5	114956	12242
2014	12	20	10:16	9.2	11.2	11.1	12.2	322	0.35	7.01	-19.1	21.7	114960	12242
2014	12	20	15:45	9.2	8.6	8.4	17.2	316	0.28	6.73	-19.1	25.1	114961	12242
2014	12	30	15:05	4.0	0.6	0.7	2.1	6	0.05	5.93	-13.8	-15.3	114977	12251
2014	12	30	21:35	3.6	1.0	1.0	3.4	68	0.09	6.04	-13.6	-23.8	114978	12251
2015	1	1	0:00	2.0	0.1	0.1	-0.2	4	0.01	5.35	-13.6	-7.5	114983	12251
2015	1	1	5:00	1.7	0.1	0.1	3.5	34	0.03	4.99	-13.6	-6.5	114984	12251
2015	1	1	10:00	1.8	0.2	0.2	4.4	31	0.04	4.84	-13.6	-3.8	114985	12251
2015	1	1	15:00	1.8	0.1	0.1	4.1	16	0.04	4.74	-13.6	-1.1	114986	12251
2015	1	1	18:12	1.8	0.2	0.2	1.8	9	0.05	4.77	-13.6	0.7	114987	12251
2015	1	1	23:05	1.7	0.2	0.2	3.8	17	0.04	4.85	-13.6	4.2	114988	12251
2015	1	2	3:30	1.8	0.2	0.2	1.2	19	0.05	4.43	-13.6	5.8	114989	12251
2015	1	2	8:30	2.0	0.3	0.3	6.5	72	0.07	4.28	-13.6	8.6	114990	12251
2015	1	2	13:30	1.7	0.1	0.1	-0.8	6	0.03	4.23	-13.6	11.3	114991	12251
2015	1	2	22:00	1.6	0.1	0.1	0.3	11	0.03	4.05	-13.6	15.2	114993	12251
2015	1	6	10:56	3.0	0.1	0.1	-2.5	-22	0.02	4.49	-6.6	20.4	115001	12253
2015	1	7	16:51	3.0	0.4	0.4	0.8	31	0.05	5.55	-7.0	24.4	115022	12253
2015	1	8	10:45	6.5	-0.2	-0.2	7.0	60	-0.01	6.56	5.5	6.0	115026	12257
2015	1	8	14:25	7.8	-0.3	-0.3	0.6	-20	-0.01	6.86	5.4	5.0	115027	12257
2015	1	8	19:15	8.7	-1.3	-1.2	2.8	-62	-0.04	6.81	5.4	6.4	115028	12257

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	1	9	9:20	9.1	-3.4	-3.3	-0.4	-68	-0.10	7.39	5.5	18.6	115029	12257
2015	1	9	13:23	9.1	-2.9	-2.9	-0.6	-92	-0.09	7.29	5.5	20.8	115030	12257
2015	1	9	18:20	8.9	-3.6	-3.6	0.7	-79	-0.11	7.05	5.5	23.6	115035	12257
2015	1	9	23:00	9.0	-3.5	-3.4	1.1	-56	-0.11	7.08	5.5	26.2	115036	12257
2015	1	11	7:06	6.8	-1.2	-1.3	4.1	58	-0.06	6.05	5.5	27.1	115047	12257
2015	1	11	9:06	6.8	-1.3	-1.4	4.6	50	-0.06	5.94	5.4	25.7	115048	12257
2015	1	11	23:44	5.4	-1.1	-1.0	7.8	5	-0.07	5.48	4.9	24.1	115057	12257
2015	1	14	6:15	4.4	1.5	1.5	4.2	75	0.11	6.25	-14.8	-3.0	115066	12259
2015	1	14	9:15	4.5	1.4	1.4	3.8	74	0.10	6.04	-14.8	-1.3	115067	12259
2015	1	14	10:42	4.4	1.5	1.5	5.2	71	0.11	6.03	-14.8	-0.5	115068	12259
2015	1	14	12:15	4.3	1.3	1.2	3.2	77	0.10	5.95	-14.8	0.3	115069	12259
2015	1	14	18:20	4.3	0.9	0.9	2.4	89	0.07	5.77	-14.8	3.6	115073	12259
2015	1	14	21:19	4.1	0.8	0.7	-0.9	84	0.07	5.79	-14.8	5.3	115074	12259
2015	1	15	0:19	4.0	0.9	0.8	4.4	83	0.07	5.81	-14.8	6.9	115075	12259
2015	1	15	2:19	3.9	0.9	0.9	-0.1	81	0.08	5.73	-14.8	8.0	115076	12259
2015	1	15	5:20	3.9	0.9	0.9	3.2	63	0.08	5.66	-14.8	7.1	115077	12259
2015	1	29	12:15	4.7	0.6	0.6	6.4	56	0.04	7.25	-9.2	18.1	115111	12268
2015	2	3	12:17	3.2	-0.1	-0.1	-2.1	-4	-0.01	5.08	7.5	-10.6	115113	12277
2015	2	3	13:29	3.0	0.4	0.4	5.0	55	0.07	3.37	7.5	7.6	115114	12277
2015	2	3	21:30	3.4	0.5	0.5	7.0	111	0.09	3.54	7.2	5.9	115115	12277
2015	2	4	14:03	3.8	1.2	1.1	9.4	133	0.17	3.70	7.3	19.1	115118	12277
2015	2	7	3:46	3.2	1.0	0.9	10.0	118	0.13	4.74	-8.4	-2.0	115128	12280
2015	2	7	7:00	3.2	0.8	0.7	4.8	86	0.10	4.75	-8.4	-0.3	115129	12280
2015	2	7	12:30	2.5	0.7	0.6	6.0	127	0.11	4.63	-8.4	2.6	115132	12280
2015	2	7	14:01	2.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	60	0.10	4.56	-8.4	2.5	115133	12280
2015	2	7	15:37	2.4	0.8	0.7	5.2	58	0.13	4.79	-8.4	4.4	115134	12280
2015	2	14	14:45	2.6	0.2	0.2	4.1	0	0.03	5.06	6.7	2.7	115166	12282
2015	3	9	20:48	5.9	5.0	4.7	10.1	370	0.36	4.66	-20.0	-21.6	115255	12297
2015	3	10	7:45	6.7	6.2	5.8	18.3	626	0.41	4.49	-19.6	-18.7	115262	12297
2015	3	10	11:04	6.4	5.7	5.3	20.6	588	0.39	4.57	-18.1	-19.1	115264	12297
2015	3	11	3:15	7.3	6.6	6.2	24.5	660	0.39	4.60	-17.1	-28.2	115267	12297
2015	3	11	8:10	7.7	6.7	6.4	17.9	571	0.36	4.74	-17.1	-25.5	115268	12297
2015	3	11	22:01	9.2	8.1	7.8	14.6	712	0.35	4.95	-17.1	-17.8	115271	12297

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	3	11	22:35	8.7	8.5	8.2	16.3	724	0.40	4.89	-17.1	-17.5	115272	12297
2015	3	12	3:22	9.4	9.4	9.1	23.2	826	0.41	4.85	-17.2	-14.8	115273	12297
2015	3	12	4:43	9.5	9.2	9.0	15.0	778	0.40	4.88	-17.2	-14.1	115274	12297
2015	3	12	10:37	10.7	8.2	7.8	25.9	856	0.31	4.90	-17.2	-10.8	115275	12297
2015	3	12	13:52	9.0	8.4	8.0	23.8	771	0.39	4.78	-17.2	-4.6	115276	12297
2015	3	12	15:50	10.0	7.2	6.9	16.2	756	0.29	4.89	-17.2	-4.6	115277	12297
2015	3	12	21:00	9.5	7.0	6.6	15.1	701	0.30	4.83	-17.2	-5.1	115278	12297
2015	3	12	21:48	7.5	7.7	7.3	14.5	614	0.43	4.74	-17.2	-4.7	115279	12297
2015	3	13	3:01	8.6	6.5	6.2	21.4	732	0.32	4.68	-17.2	-1.8	115280	12297
2015	3	13	10:30	7.5	5.6	5.2	17.0	639	0.32	4.54	-17.2	2.4	115282	12297
2015	3	13	20:00	7.2	5.0	4.6	18.6	639	0.30	4.61	-17.2	5.0	115283	12297
2015	3	14	1:50	6.9	5.2	4.9	11.2	498	0.31	4.78	-17.2	10.8	115285	12297
2015	3	15	9:30	5.9	7.7	7.5	11.1	444	0.43	5.94	-17.3	28.1	115292	12297
2015	3	16	23:00	3.9	4.2	4.1	1.5	250	0.41	5.28	-19.0	24.5	115302	12297
2015	3	22	21:56	2.0	0.1	0.1	1.9	10	0.02	5.02	19.5	-4.7	115343	12303
2015	3	23	2:15	1.9	0.1	0.1	3.4	13	0.02	5.08	19.5	-2.4	115344	12303
2015	3	31	10:33	5.0	1.1	1.1	1.6	35	0.06	7.41	-13.8	25.0	115349	12305
2015	4	7	23:02	3.4	1.1	0.9	16.3	226	0.16	3.90	-13.3	-4.3	115360	12320
2015	4	15	6:32	6.2	-6.9	-6.8	-1.9	-259	-0.35	6.24	10.3	-15.8	115398	12321
2015	4	15	11:30	5.3	-4.9	-4.8	-3.7	-209	-0.29	6.36	10.9	-27.6	115399	12321
2015	4	15	15:00	5.6	-5.4	-5.4	-3.0	-226	-0.30	6.42	10.9	-25.7	115401	12321
2015	4	15	23:00	5.8	-5.0	-5.0	-1.9	-186	-0.28	6.23	10.9	-21.1	115402	12321
2015	4	17	13:07	4.4	-3.0	-3.0	0.0	-63	-0.24	5.59	10.9	4.2	115409	12321
2015	4	22	12:54	3.2	-0.9	-0.9	2.1	-51	-0.12	4.67	19.1	25.4	115442	12324
2015	4	22	19:00	2.8	-0.5	-0.5	1.4	-25	-0.08	4.59	18.7	21.1	115444	12324
2015	4	26	9:30	1.0	-0.4	-0.4	-1.2	-12	-0.22	3.76	20.1	-23.6	115456	12333
2015	5	8	12:00	8.9	-3.5	-3.6	13.9	174	-0.10	7.38	11.0	-25.1	115481	12339
2015	5	9	12:30	8.1	-4.0	-4.0	0.9	23	-0.15	6.41	11.3	-16.5	115483	12339
2015	5	9	16:05	7.4	-1.5	-1.5	17.6	79	-0.06	6.57	11.4	-14.9	115484	12339
2015	5	9	22:30	7.8	-2.7	-2.7	3.5	16	-0.11	6.10	11.6	-23.2	115485	12339
2015	5	10	3:15	6.4	-0.6	-0.7	14.0	127	-0.03	6.40	11.6	-20.6	115486	12339
2015	6	9	11:29	3.1	0.7	0.6	1.7	50	0.07	5.84	3.7	-10.0	115563	12362
2015	6	9	13:06	3.1	0.8	0.7	1.9	67	0.09	5.59	3.7	-9.1	115564	12362

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	6	9	15:25	1.9	0.7	0.7	1.1	50	0.14	4.91	3.7	-7.9	115566	12362
2015	6	9	16:36	2.1	0.9	0.8	0.4	51	0.16	5.17	3.6	-6.3	115567	12362
2015	6	9	18:24	2.3	0.9	0.9	2.0	53	0.15	5.50	3.7	-6.2	115568	12362
2015	6	9	19:50	2.3	0.8	0.8	2.0	30	0.14	5.45	3.7	-5.3	115569	12362
2015	6	9	21:25	2.2	0.8	0.8	4.8	48	0.14	5.42	3.7	-4.5	115570	12362
2015	6	10	14:10	1.7	0.8	0.8	2.5	35	0.17	5.27	3.7	4.8	115571	12362
2015	6	10	15:30	1.8	0.8	0.8	4.5	44	0.18	5.14	3.7	5.6	115572	12362
2015	6	10	17:10	1.7	0.7	0.7	-1.1	31	0.16	5.22	3.7	6.5	115573	12362
2015	6	10	19:04	1.7	0.8	0.8	1.0	30	0.17	5.28	3.7	7.6	115574	12362
2015	6	11	14:17	1.5	0.5	0.5	3.1	38	0.13	4.93	3.7	18.3	115575	12362
2015	6	11	16:10	1.5	0.4	0.4	1.0	20	0.11	5.02	3.7	10.2	115576	12362
2015	6	11	18:15	1.3	0.5	0.4	1.4	30	0.13	5.14	3.7	20.3	115577	12362
2015	6	11	19:26	1.4	0.4	0.4	1.1	20	0.12	5.17	3.7	21.1	115578	12362
2015	6	11	21:05	1.3	0.4	0.3	-0.3	11	0.11	5.09	3.6	13.6	115579	12362
2015	6	16	12:31	6.7	2.3	2.2	13.1	151	0.10	6.58	-21.5	-12.3	115584	12367
2015	6	16	15:40	5.3	1.7	1.7	1.7	25	0.09	7.32	-21.5	-10.5	115586	12367
2015	6	16	18:55	3.9	0.6	0.6	5.5	48	0.06	5.88	-21.5	-7.2	115587	12367
2015	6	17	1:29	5.3	1.7	1.7	2.8	61	0.09	6.92	-21.5	-5.2	115588	12367
2015	6	17	4:46	3.6	0.2	0.2	7.5	16	0.02	5.54	-21.3	-3.4	115589	12367
2015	6	17	8:02	5.2	1.5	1.5	3.8	54	0.08	6.69	-21.5	-1.6	115590	12367
2015	6	17	19:40	3.0	-0.2	-0.2	7.1	28	-0.03	4.80	-21.5	4.5	115591	12367
2015	6	18	0:30	4.5	2.0	2.0	9.8	61	0.13	6.71	-21.5	7.2	115592	12367
2015	6	18	7:00	2.8	-0.3	-0.3	1.5	-5	-0.05	4.71	-21.5	10.8	115593	12367
2015	6	20	10:21	11.2	-15.8	-15.6	2.2	-314	-0.38	7.44	10.0	-24.2	115620	12371
2015	6	20	14:47	12.5	-11.9	-11.7	4.0	-261	-0.28	6.67	10.0	-21.5	115621	12371
2015	6	20	19:41	12.4	-18.8	-18.6	-8.3	-366	-0.40	7.57	10.0	-18.8	115622	12371
2015	6	21	0:37	12.3	-20.1	-19.8	-2.9	-335	-0.44	7.42	10.0	-12.1	115624	12371
2015	6	21	6:11	11.0	-21.0	-20.9	1.7	-319	-0.51	7.46	10.0	-11.2	115626	12371
2015	6	21	18:40	12.7	-24.1	-24.0	-8.2	-389	-0.50	7.63	10.0	-6.0	115627	12371
2015	6	22	6:21	11.1	-19.2	-19.1	-3.8	-302	-0.48	7.22	10.0	0.3	115628	12371
2015	6	22	7:45	11.1	-16.9	-16.8	3.6	-278	-0.42	7.14	10.0	-0.0	115629	12371
2015	6	22	11:03	12.3	-20.0	-19.9	-5.0	-319	-0.44	7.39	10.0	3.0	115631	12371
2015	6	23	8:21	11.5	-18.5	-18.5	-2.1	-234	-0.45	7.03	10.0	13.6	115640	12371

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	6	23	14:55	11.3	-17.9	-17.9	-0.8	-225	-0.45	7.07	9.5	18.0	115645	12371
2015	6	24	4:02	10.5	-12.9	-13.0	6.4	-93	-0.37	6.60	9.5	24.8	115650	12371
2015	6	24	7:18	9.8	-12.2	-12.2	6.5	-111	-0.37	6.68	9.5	27.1	115652	12371
2015	6	24	12:14	9.5	-11.1	-11.2	8.3	-49	-0.35	6.59	9.7	17.3	115653	12371
2015	6	24	18:48	8.2	-8.4	-8.4	7.7	-40	-0.33	6.18	9.7	20.3	115655	12371
2015	6	25	18:09	6.7	-7.1	-7.1	3.3	-113	-0.37	5.70	10.0	22.6	115662	12371
2015	6	26	11:47	5.6	-4.5	-4.6	5.3	-34	-0.29	5.45	10.3	27.0	115667	12371
2015	7	1	11:29	2.0	-0.0	-0.0	2.0	12	-0.00	5.01	12.2	-22.4	115674	12373
2015	7	4	0:09	2.8	-0.2	-0.2	2.5	-5	-0.04	4.70	12.6	-3.5	115683	12373
2015	7	4	6:43	2.8	-0.2	-0.2	4.1	-3	-0.04	4.55	12.6	0.1	115684	12373
2015	7	4	13:16	3.0	-0.2	-0.2	4.4	15	-0.03	4.35	12.6	3.8	115685	12373
2015	7	4	19:50	2.7	-0.4	-0.3	4.0	-10	-0.06	4.25	12.6	7.4	115686	12373
2015	7	5	2:23	2.5	-0.2	-0.2	6.8	20	-0.05	4.03	12.6	11.0	115687	12373
2015	7	5	10:35	2.3	-0.1	-0.1	5.1	14	-0.02	3.84	12.6	15.6	115688	12373
2015	7	5	18:47	2.2	-0.2	-0.2	5.0	11	-0.04	3.66	12.6	20.1	115689	12373
2015	7	6	2:59	2.0	0.0	0.0	4.4	35	0.01	3.37	12.6	24.6	115690	12373
2015	7	7	10:08	5.2	-2.4	-2.4	3.6	-15	-0.13	6.90	11.8	-25.1	115694	12381
2015	7	7	15:06	4.2	-0.3	-0.2	4.8	-26	-0.02	5.80	11.8	-22.3	115695	12381
2015	7	7	20:07	5.9	-3.2	-3.1	-2.9	-102	-0.16	6.76	11.9	-11.0	115697	12381
2015	7	8	0:57	4.4	-0.1	-0.1	6.7	1	-0.01	5.89	11.8	-16.9	115698	12381
2015	7	8	9:05	6.0	-3.3	-3.3	1.3	-104	-0.15	7.12	11.8	-10.8	115700	12381
2015	7	8	14:00	4.1	-0.6	-0.6	2.3	24	-0.04	6.42	11.8	-9.6	115701	12381
2015	7	8	19:05	5.9	-1.9	-1.9	3.5	-34	-0.09	6.96	11.8	-7.0	115702	12381
2015	7	8	23:54	3.7	-0.3	-0.3	2.4	3	-0.03	6.67	11.8	-4.2	115703	12381
2015	7	9	9:44	5.8	-2.9	-2.9	-0.5	-108	-0.14	6.90	11.8	1.3	115706	12381
2015	7	10	7:00	3.2	0.4	0.4	-0.1	25	0.04	6.25	11.8	13.1	115710	12381
2015	7	10	21:48	5.3	-1.4	-1.4	3.4	-38	-0.08	6.77	11.9	16.3	115713	12381
2015	7	11	2:40	2.8	0.6	0.6	4.5	49	0.07	6.22	11.8	24.0	115714	12381
2015	7	11	7:35	4.6	-1.2	-1.2	1.3	-29	-0.08	6.53	12.0	19.2	115715	12381
2015	7	16	0:45	2.2	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-11	-0.04	5.20	9.4	-19.4	115730	12386
2015	7	16	4:00	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	-1.6	-13	-0.03	4.57	9.2	-26.2	115732	12386
2015	7	20	0:01	1.2	0.2	0.1	3.4	20	0.07	3.89	13.7	-20.5	115756	12387
2015	7	20	4:48	2.2	-0.2	-0.1	3.8	5	-0.03	5.49	13.8	-10.9	115757	12387

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	7	20	9:48	2.2	-0.0	-0.0	4.0	18	-0.00	5.62	13.7	-14.8	115758	12387
2015	7	20	14:40	2.3	-0.0	-0.0	-0.2	3	-0.00	5.62	13.7	-12.2	115759	12387
2015	7	21	2:10	2.4	0.1	0.0	0.9	33	0.01	5.67	13.7	-5.8	115760	12387
2015	7	21	23:23	2.0	-0.0	-0.1	2.6	24	-0.00	5.51	13.7	3.7	115761	12387
2015	7	22	7:35	2.0	-0.1	-0.1	2.9	14	-0.01	5.37	13.7	10.5	115762	12387
2015	7	22	10:51	1.9	-0.1	-0.0	3.5	11	-0.01	5.28	13.7	12.3	115763	12387
2015	7	22	16:00	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.7	-1	-0.02	5.43	13.8	11.9	115764	12387
2015	7	23	0:03	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.0	14	-0.02	5.71	13.8	16.0	115765	12387
2015	7	28	11:20	3.1	0.4	0.4	8.7	83	0.04	6.73	-18.0	18.4	115787	12390
2015	7	28	12:57	3.1	0.2	0.2	3.1	40	0.02	6.80	-17.8	14.0	115788	12390
2015	7	28	14:35	3.2	0.0	-0.0	0.2	37	0.00	6.66	-18.0	20.2	115789	12390
2015	7	28	16:20	3.1	-0.1	-0.1	3.3	53	-0.01	6.66	-18.0	21.1	115790	12390
2015	7	28	19:42	2.9	-0.3	-0.4	1.6	15	-0.04	6.73	-18.0	22.8	115791	12390
2015	7	28	22:53	1.5	-0.3	-0.3	2.1	19	-0.08	5.19	-18.0	24.7	115792	12390
2015	7	29	2:04	2.5	-0.4	-0.4	1.8	13	-0.05	6.84	-18.0	26.4	115793	12390
2015	7	29	6:59	2.3	-0.4	-0.4	1.6	17	-0.05	6.83	-18.0	29.1	115794	12390
2015	7	30	2:41	1.7	-0.1	-0.1	1.4	12	-0.01	6.59	-16.9	19.9	115797	12390
2015	7	30	9:13	1.5	-0.1	-0.1	0.9	7	-0.02	6.33	-16.8	23.0	115798	12390
2015	8	4	17:10	2.6	0.3	0.3	1.1	6	0.04	5.39	10.4	-6.1	115812	12394
2015	8	4	18:47	2.5	0.3	0.3	2.9	10	0.05	5.53	10.4	-4.6	115813	12394
2015	8	4	20:24	2.6	0.3	0.4	3.4	9	0.05	5.48	10.4	-4.3	115814	12394
2015	8	5	10:57	2.6	-0.1	-0.0	1.0	13	-0.01	5.11	10.6	3.8	115816	12394
2015	8	5	17:45	2.5	-0.2	-0.1	-1.0	-31	-0.03	5.14	10.4	7.5	115817	12394
2015	8	5	19:22	2.5	-0.1	-0.1	1.6	-12	-0.02	5.12	10.4	8.4	115818	12394
2015	8	5	19:52	2.4	-0.1	-0.1	1.5	0	-0.02	5.09	10.4	6.5	115819	12394
2015	8	6	11:32	2.5	-0.3	-0.2	-0.8	-19	-0.04	5.01	10.6	17.4	115821	12394
2015	8	6	17:05	2.4	0.1	0.1	0.9	0	0.01	5.17	10.4	20.4	115822	12394
2015	8	6	18:20	2.4	0.1	0.1	-0.6	-4	0.02	5.14	10.4	21.1	115823	12394
2015	8	6	19:57	2.4	-0.0	-0.0	-0.1	-13	-0.00	5.07	10.4	22.0	115824	12394
2015	8	7	10:29	2.3	-0.0	0.0	0.6	0	-0.01	4.78	11.2	16.3	115826	12394
2015	8	7	19:25	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	-2.1	-13	-0.02	4.70	11.2	17.0	115830	12394
2015	8	18	16:35	1.9	0.0	-0.0	4.4	11	0.00	5.41	-11.0	10.8	115894	12401
2015	8	18	21:06	1.9	-0.2	-0.2	6.5	27	-0.04	5.52	-11.0	13.3	115896	12401

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	8	19	10:35	1.7	-0.4	-0.4	1.6	14	-0.09	5.39	-11.0	20.7	115908	12401
2015	8	19	21:05	1.5	-0.4	-0.4	0.9	-3	-0.10	5.44	-11.0	26.5	115910	12401
2015	8	22	14:46	8.8	3.6	3.6	14.8	287	0.15	5.52	-16.2	-17.5	115934	12403
2015	8	22	18:17	9.2	3.3	3.1	19.5	298	0.13	5.36	-16.2	-15.5	115935	12403
2015	8	25	10:31	7.4	6.5	6.4	6.2	196	0.24	7.31	-16.2	19.7	115946	12403
2015	8	25	12:00	8.7	2.1	2.1	23.2	176	0.07	7.40	-16.2	20.5	115947	12403
2015	8	25	13:45	6.5	-1.1	-1.3	34.2	306	-0.07	5.13	-16.2	21.4	115948	12403
2015	8	25	14:50	7.8	4.7	4.6	12.1	201	0.18	6.71	-16.2	22.0	115949	12403
2015	8	25	18:20	7.1	5.1	4.9	12.4	267	0.21	6.72	-15.8	14.4	115950	12403
2015	8	25	20:00	9.2	1.3	1.3	15.8	86	0.04	7.58	-16.2	24.9	115951	12403
2015	8	25	23:10	8.4	1.1	1.0	12.3	86	0.03	7.79	-15.6	14.3	115952	12403
2015	8	26	2:20	6.4	1.5	1.5	6.0	53	0.08	6.06	-15.6	15.6	115953	12403
2015	8	26	5:30	7.4	-0.7	-0.7	13.7	146	-0.03	6.82	-15.7	21.1	115954	12403
2015	8	26	8:35	5.3	4.4	4.3	13.5	201	0.25	6.66	-17.1	28.9	115955	12403
2015	8	26	23:42	4.0	2.3	2.2	6.3	103	0.18	6.24	-16.1	21.1	115963	12403
2015	8	27	19:28	4.8	-1.3	-1.2	3.8	-45	-0.08	6.74	-11.0	28.4	115972	12403
2015	9	9	9:21	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.6	1	-0.03	4.11	-7.4	-15.7	116024	12412
2015	9	10	8:06	1.0	-0.2	-0.2	1.2	-5	-0.10	4.10	-8.2	-17.5	116027	12412
2015	9	10	8:31	1.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.4	-5	-0.08	4.11	-8.2	-17.3	116028	12412
2015	9	10	8:56	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-9	-0.06	4.14	-8.0	-11.6	116029	12412
2015	9	10	9:40	1.0	-0.2	-0.2	1.5	-2	-0.09	4.13	-7.9	-9.2	116030	12412
2015	9	10	15:12	0.5	0.0	0.0	2.6	8	0.01	3.94	-8.4	-10.6	116031	12412
2015	9	10	16:20	1.5	-0.3	-0.2	3.0	0	-0.09	4.24	-8.4	-10.0	116032	12412
2015	9	12	13:36	5.0	-2.2	-2.2	2.3	-38	-0.14	6.20	-11.5	26.6	116038	12414
2015	9	18	6:15	2.2	-1.5	-1.5	1.9	-25	-0.28	4.91	-21.1	17.1	116081	12415
2015	9	18	10:06	3.6	-2.4	-2.4	2.0	-66	-0.28	4.82	-20.6	11.8	116083	12415
2015	9	18	17:00	3.5	-1.6	-1.6	-0.3	-36	-0.18	5.15	-20.7	14.0	116084	12415
2015	9	18	18:17	1.9	-1.4	-1.3	-0.2	-50	-0.28	5.15	-21.1	23.6	116085	12415
2015	9	19	5:46	1.6	-1.2	-1.2	-1.2	-34	-0.27	5.38	-21.1	29.8	116086	12415
2015	9	19	18:36	4.0	1.9	1.9	2.7	55	0.14	6.82	-17.3	0.6	116088	12418
2015	9	19	21:35	3.9	2.1	2.1	-1.1	49	0.15	6.91	-17.3	1.8	116089	12418
2015	9	29	0:00	7.8	-0.6	-0.7	17.8	77	-0.03	5.87	-21.2	15.7	116119	12422
2015	9	29	4:40	7.3	-2.7	-2.6	7.4	-62	-0.14	5.09	-21.1	18.6	116120	12422

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	9	30	6:40	4.6	-2.5	-2.5	3.6	-23	-0.21	5.08	-17.9	25.3	116129	12422
2015	9	30	12:00	3.4	-1.2	-1.1	0.7	-4	-0.11	6.51	-17.6	24.4	116130	12422
2015	10	17	15:56	5.3	5.3	5.2	15.4	325	0.40	5.11	-11.2	-25.7	116205	12434
2015	10	18	4:35	4.9	5.2	5.1	14.5	270	0.40	5.33	-11.0	-15.2	116206	12434
2015	10	18	6:15	4.7	4.8	4.7	13.2	234	0.39	5.25	-11.3	-21.1	116207	12434
2015	10	18	6:58	4.7	4.9	4.9	15.2	261	0.39	5.36	-11.3	-20.1	116208	12434
2015	10	18	9:00	4.6	4.8	4.7	16.0	242	0.39	5.35	-11.3	-19.6	116209	12434
2015	10	20	2:04	3.5	2.9	2.9	8.8	127	0.32	5.22	-11.3	3.1	116210	12434
2015	10	20	4:00	3.2	2.7	2.7	6.7	105	0.32	5.22	-11.3	4.2	116211	12434
2015	10	26	8:48	2.4	0.3	0.3	-0.8	11	0.06	4.85	8.2	21.0	116239	12436
2015	10	27	16:28	1.0	0.1	0.1	3.7	37	0.08	3.21	18.1	9.8	116243	12440
2015	10	28	17:03	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	8	0.02	2.58	18.1	23.4	116246	12440
2015	11	3	14:15	7.5	0.9	0.9	3.0	54	0.04	5.82	5.8	-12.6	116255	12443
2015	11	3	16:01	5.1	-0.0	-0.0	-1.4	10	-0.00	5.50	5.8	-11.8	116256	12443
2015	11	3	21:05	4.8	-0.1	-0.1	4.4	-11	-0.00	5.33	5.8	-5.7	116257	12443
2015	11	3	22:50	4.7	0.1	0.1	-3.9	-45	0.01	5.28	5.8	-8.0	116258	12443
2015	11	4	1:10	4.6	0.1	0.1	5.5	9	0.00	5.26	5.8	-6.7	116259	12443
2015	11	4	3:10	4.5	0.0	0.1	-2.7	-28	0.00	5.27	5.8	-5.6	116260	12443
2015	11	4	5:00	4.4	-0.0	0.0	4.0	-24	-0.00	5.22	5.8	-4.6	116261	12443
2015	11	4	6:21	4.3	0.1	0.1	5.9	-1	0.01	5.17	5.8	-3.8	116262	12443
2015	11	4	10:06	5.1	0.3	0.3	9.9	68	0.02	5.47	5.7	-4.5	116263	12443
2015	11	4	12:30	4.4	0.1	0.1	12.7	57	0.01	5.28	5.7	-3.2	116264	12443
2015	11	4	15:00	5.0	1.3	1.3	18.7	125	0.09	5.45	5.7	-1.8	116265	12443
2015	11	4	18:10	2.8	0.5	0.5	9.2	80	0.08	4.56	5.7	-0.1	116266	12443
2015	11	4	21:30	2.7	0.4	0.4	4.7	63	0.07	4.55	5.7	1.7	116267	12443
2015	11	5	0:30	2.7	0.4	0.4	12.8	110	0.07	4.53	5.7	3.4	116268	12443
2015	11	5	3:30	2.7	0.5	0.4	9.9	86	0.07	4.53	5.7	5.0	116269	12443
2015	11	5	6:35	2.6	0.3	0.2	8.3	92	0.05	4.42	5.7	6.7	116270	12443
2015	11	6	16:00	3.9	0.2	0.2	5.3	28	0.02	5.45	8.1	18.9	116277	12443
2015	11	7	1:16	3.5	0.2	0.2	4.8	25	0.02	5.33	8.2	23.8	116280	12443
2015	11	11	10:01	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	5.4	34	-0.04	4.01	4.8	1.6	116292	12448
2015	11	11	23:30	1.0	-0.4	-0.4	-1.1	-26	-0.18	4.24	-14.5	-9.9	116294	12449
2015	11	19	13:28	1.9	-0.3	-0.3	0.7	-7	-0.09	4.09	4.6	6.9	116305	12456

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	11	20	12:01	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	2.3	3	-0.06	4.27	4.6	19.4	116326	12456
2015	11	21	0:00	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	-1.9	-16	-0.08	4.09	4.8	17.2	116327	12456
2015	11	24	9:57	2.2	-0.6	-0.6	-0.2	-12	-0.11	4.74	11.7	-20.0	116331	12457
2015	11	24	13:00	2.1	-0.5	-0.5	-1.8	-14	-0.10	4.60	11.7	-14.2	116332	12457
2015	11	24	17:00	2.0	-0.5	-0.5	-3.6	-25	-0.11	4.67	11.7	-8.8	116333	12457
2015	11	24	21:35	1.9	-0.4	-0.4	-4.0	-35	-0.10	4.62	11.7	-8.7	116334	12457
2015	11	25	0:35	1.9	-0.5	-0.4	-4.7	-44	-0.10	4.58	11.7	-11.9	116335	12457
2015	11	25	3:45	1.8	-0.5	-0.5	-3.5	-33	-0.11	4.55	11.7	-6.7	116336	12457
2015	11	25	7:00	1.7	-0.4	-0.4	-0.6	-25	-0.10	4.49	11.7	-6.6	116337	12457
2015	11	25	12:02	1.7	-0.3	-0.3	-0.5	-19	-0.08	4.48	11.7	-5.6	116338	12457
2015	11	25	15:45	1.7	-0.3	-0.2	0.2	-25	-0.07	4.33	11.7	-3.5	116339	12457
2015	11	25	19:00	1.6	-0.2	-0.2	2.4	0	-0.06	4.05	11.7	-1.7	116340	12457
2015	11	26	7:35	1.7	-0.4	-0.4	1.5	-5	-0.11	4.22	11.7	5.3	116341	12457
2015	11	26	12:00	1.8	-0.4	-0.4	2.1	2	-0.11	4.01	11.7	7.7	116342	12457
2015	11	26	16:20	1.6	-0.3	-0.3	3.9	14	-0.09	4.09	11.7	9.1	116343	12457
2015	11	26	22:45	1.7	-0.3	-0.3	6.3	21	-0.08	4.13	11.7	13.7	116344	12457
2015	11	27	3:30	1.7	-0.3	-0.3	4.7	13	-0.07	4.08	11.7	12.9	116345	12457
2015	11	27	8:15	1.7	-0.2	-0.2	5.3	18	-0.06	4.07	11.7	13.2	116346	12457
2015	11	27	12:15	1.6	-0.3	-0.3	2.9	5	-0.08	4.07	11.7	21.1	116347	12457
2015	11	27	15:15	1.6	-0.2	-0.2	3.1	15	-0.07	4.05	11.7	22.8	116348	12457
2015	11	27	18:30	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	3.4	18	-0.06	3.91	11.7	25.6	116349	12457
2015	11	27	23:30	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	2.9	9	-0.08	3.92	11.7	27.4	116350	12457
2015	12	1	16:00	0.6	0.0	0.0	2.6	17	0.07	2.33	3.1	14.1	116354	12459
2015	12	1	17:30	0.6	0.1	0.1	1.4	9	0.08	2.36	3.1	15.0	116355	12459
2015	12	1	19:40	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.3	9	0.06	2.38	3.1	16.2	116356	12459
2015	12	16	4:43	1.1	0.2	0.1	3.0	37	0.09	3.13	-15.4	1.6	116478	12468
2015	12	16	20:06	6.5	-0.9	-0.9	0.6	-6	-0.03	8.70	13.1	-16.4	116484	12470
2015	12	17	0:29	6.5	-1.1	-1.1	-0.6	-30	-0.04	8.72	13.2	-18.4	116485	12470
2015	12	17	4:00	6.7	-1.2	-1.1	6.3	-1	-0.04	8.74	13.2	-21.8	116486	12470
2015	12	17	17:21	6.7	-0.5	-0.5	2.3	-4	-0.02	9.01	11.7	-11.3	116489	12470
2015	12	18	13:05	7.2	-1.2	-1.2	3.0	-2	-0.04	8.93	11.8	-7.8	116490	12470
2015	12	19	10:20	7.7	-3.4	-3.3	-5.6	-87	-0.10	8.41	11.8	3.8	116491	12470
2015	12	19	10:55	7.8	-3.5	-3.5	-4.0	-83	-0.10	8.78	11.8	4.1	116492	12470

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	12	19	11:30	7.6	-3.5	-3.5	-0.9	-81	-0.10	8.83	11.8	4.6	116493	12470
2015	12	19	13:01	7.8	-3.6	-3.6	-2.6	-60	-0.10	8.83	11.8	5.4	116494	12470
2015	12	19	14:00	8.1	-4.0	-4.0	-0.5	-89	-0.12	8.50	11.8	5.8	116495	12470
2015	12	19	21:39	7.8	-3.9	-3.9	-2.5	-73	-0.11	8.97	11.8	10.2	116498	12470
2015	12	19	23:14	7.7	-3.7	-3.7	-0.5	-77	-0.11	8.93	11.8	11.1	116499	12470
2015	12	20	0:38	8.2	-4.0	-3.9	-5.7	-111	-0.11	8.60	11.8	11.7	116500	12470
2015	12	20	2:13	7.6	-3.2	-3.2	-3.1	-97	-0.10	8.72	11.8	12.7	116501	12470
2015	12	20	3:51	7.5	-3.1	-3.1	-6.7	-101	-0.09	8.70	11.8	13.6	116502	12470
2015	12	20	7:05	7.6	-3.5	-3.4	-4.5	-89	-0.10	8.70	11.8	15.4	116503	12470
2015	12	20	8:42	7.2	-3.1	-3.1	-4.0	-87	-0.10	8.62	11.7	10.6	116504	12470
2015	12	20	10:15	7.4	-3.1	-3.1	-3.2	-73	-0.10	8.34	11.8	17.0	116505	12470
2015	12	20	11:30	7.3	-2.7	-2.7	-3.1	-61	-0.09	8.65	11.8	17.9	116506	12470
2015	12	20	15:49	7.4	-3.4	-3.4	-3.4	-83	-0.10	8.75	11.8	20.2	116508	12470
2015	12	20	21:04	7.6	-3.2	-3.1	0.4	-69	-0.10	8.62	11.8	23.2	116510	12470
2015	12	20	22:14	7.6	-3.4	-3.4	-2.1	-82	-0.10	8.63	11.8	23.8	116511	12470
2015	12	21	0:01	7.6	-3.2	-3.1	1.1	-63	-0.10	8.57	11.7	14.7	116512	12470
2015	12	21	3:00	7.8	-2.8	-2.8	0.8	-64	-0.09	8.25	11.8	26.3	116513	12470
2015	12	21	4:25	7.6	-2.8	-2.8	-2.0	-64	-0.09	8.45	11.8	27.2	116514	12470
2015	12	21	16:22	7.3	-2.3	-2.3	-0.2	-61	-0.08	8.19	11.5	18.0	116518	12470
2015	12	24	6:36	2.6	0.8	0.8	4.6	47	0.13	4.80	2.1	-24.7	116522	12472
2015	12	25	3:34	5.8	4.2	4.1	6.1	240	0.25	5.74	-22.8	-19.9	116529	12473
2015	12	25	15:32	5.9	4.5	4.4	6.8	220	0.26	5.79	-22.8	-29.8	116531	12473
2015	12	25	18:42	6.1	4.6	4.5	13.5	250	0.26	5.72	-22.8	-28.1	116532	12473
2015	12	26	2:51	4.7	1.7	1.6	8.3	161	0.14	5.07	-22.8	-23.7	116535	12473
2015	12	26	6:15	5.5	2.5	2.4	14.6	253	0.18	4.98	-22.8	-21.8	116537	12473
2015	12	26	14:40	3.4	2.4	2.3	20.2	262	0.34	4.25	-22.8	-17.8	116540	12473
2015	12	27	18:30	3.9	0.7	0.7	17.3	169	0.08	4.56	-22.8	-2.3	116549	12473
2015	12	27	21:32	3.3	1.7	1.6	17.1	235	0.27	3.80	-22.8	-0.7	116550	12473
2015	12	28	0:30	3.9	0.5	0.4	12.1	113	0.06	4.51	-22.7	0.9	116551	12473
2015	12	28	3:42	3.9	0.7	0.6	9.7	140	0.08	4.46	-22.7	2.6	116552	12473
2015	12	28	6:56	3.8	0.9	0.8	11.9	187	0.11	4.47	-22.7	4.4	116553	12473
2015	12	28	11:00	4.1	2.9	2.6	22.3	402	0.37	3.81	-22.8	6.6	116554	12473
2015	12	28	16:00	3.8	3.2	3.0	18.6	362	0.42	3.98	-22.7	8.2	116555	12473

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2015	12	28	20:30	3.5	3.0	2.9	29.8	382	0.43	4.06	-22.8	11.7	116556	12473
2015	12	29	0:00	3.7	2.7	2.6	12.4	262	0.32	4.54	-22.8	13.6	116557	12473
2015	12	29	4:17	2.6	0.8	0.8	12.4	98	0.15	4.15	-22.8	15.9	116558	12473
2015	12	29	9:30	3.4	3.0	2.8	16.0	350	0.42	4.16	-22.8	12.8	116559	12473
2015	12	29	11:36	5.6	5.0	4.9	7.9	255	0.30	5.93	-20.3	24.7	116560	12473
2015	12	29	16:12	5.3	4.5	4.4	12.8	208	0.28	6.06	-20.3	24.9	116561	12473
2015	12	30	8:05	4.2	3.0	3.0	6.7	143	0.25	5.85	-20.6	19.8	116565	12473
2015	12	30	16:47	3.7	2.5	2.5	2.2	84	0.23	5.88	-20.8	18.2	116567	12473
2015	12	31	3:49	2.8	1.7	1.7	1.6	53	0.21	5.82	-20.9	24.8	116569	12473
2016	1	8	18:50	3.4	0.7	0.7	1.0	17	0.06	6.12	1.1	-23.7	116593	12480
2016	1	9	1:30	3.5	0.8	0.9	1.5	23	0.08	6.23	1.3	-24.9	116594	12480
2016	1	10	6:28	3.6	0.8	0.8	0.2	32	0.07	5.99	1.8	-16.3	116599	12480
2016	1	12	15:17	3.2	-0.3	-0.3	3.4	-16	-0.03	5.65	16.8	2.4	116604	12483
2016	1	12	18:13	3.2	-0.3	-0.3	1.6	-29	-0.04	5.68	16.8	4.0	116605	12483
2016	1	12	21:15	3.1	-0.1	-0.1	7.6	2	-0.01	5.69	16.7	5.7	116606	12483
2016	1	13	0:15	3.1	-0.1	-0.1	4.6	-8	-0.02	5.69	16.8	7.4	116607	12483
2016	1	13	3:25	3.0	-0.1	-0.1	3.4	-2	-0.02	5.67	16.7	9.1	116608	12483
2016	1	13	10:00	2.9	-0.3	-0.3	1.3	-14	-0.03	5.61	16.7	11.6	116609	12483
2016	1	13	12:50	2.9	0.1	0.1	7.1	25	0.01	5.54	16.8	14.3	116610	12483
2016	1	13	15:40	2.9	0.0	0.0	4.2	7	0.00	5.55	16.6	8.2	116611	12483
2016	1	13	18:30	2.8	-0.1	-0.1	2.2	-7	-0.01	5.49	16.8	17.4	116612	12483
2016	1	13	22:00	2.6	-0.0	-0.0	-0.3	-9	-0.00	5.51	16.8	19.3	116613	12483
2016	1	20	6:16	1.1	0.1	0.1	1.2	16	0.07	3.37	-22.7	-25.2	116654	12486
2016	1	21	7:00	1.1	0.2	0.2	2.1	20	0.10	3.67	-22.2	-16.9	116659	12486
2016	1	21	10:00	2.6	-0.9	-0.9	2.3	-18	-0.10	6.28	-14.4	-16.8	116660	12487
2016	1	22	1:00	2.7	-0.5	-0.5	4.5	13	-0.07	5.94	-13.8	-24.1	116663	12487
2016	1	22	4:00	2.6	-0.7	-0.7	6.2	11	-0.09	5.87	-13.8	-22.4	116664	12487
2016	1	22	7:00	2.5	-0.7	-0.7	4.1	16	-0.09	5.64	-13.8	-20.8	116665	12487
2016	1	22	11:00	2.5	-0.8	-0.8	2.8	5	-0.11	5.59	-13.8	-18.6	116666	12487
2016	1	22	14:00	2.4	-0.8	-0.8	0.4	-11	-0.11	5.64	-13.8	-16.9	116667	12487
2016	1	22	16:00	2.3	-0.6	-0.6	2.8	9	-0.10	5.58	-13.9	-12.5	116668	12487
2016	1	22	19:00	2.2	-0.6	-0.6	2.6	2	-0.10	5.61	-13.8	-14.2	116669	12487
2016	1	23	0:00	2.1	-0.7	-0.7	0.5	-10	-0.12	5.43	-13.8	-10.3	116670	12487

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	1	23	3:00	2.1	-0.5	-0.5	-2.1	-15	-0.09	5.26	-13.8	-9.8	116671	12487
2016	1	23	6:30	2.1	-0.4	-0.4	-0.1	-7	-0.08	5.25	-13.8	-7.9	116672	12487
2016	1	23	11:00	2.2	-0.4	-0.4	3.1	12	-0.07	5.01	-13.8	-4.5	116673	12487
2016	1	23	13:00	2.1	-0.4	-0.4	3.2	11	-0.08	4.94	-13.8	-4.3	116674	12487
2016	1	23	16:30	1.9	-0.3	-0.3	3.3	3	-0.07	4.97	-13.8	-2.4	116675	12487
2016	1	23	20:00	1.8	-0.5	-0.5	0.7	-11	-0.11	4.96	-13.8	-0.5	116676	12487
2016	1	23	23:00	1.8	-0.5	-0.4	2.4	-12	-0.11	4.81	-13.8	1.2	116677	12487
2016	1	24	3:30	1.7	-0.4	-0.3	1.9	-21	-0.09	4.67	-13.8	3.7	116678	12487
2016	1	24	7:00	1.6	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-8	-0.05	4.61	-13.8	5.6	116679	12487
2016	1	24	10:00	1.6	-0.2	-0.2	-0.4	-12	-0.06	4.52	-13.8	6.0	116680	12487
2016	1	24	13:00	1.5	-0.2	-0.2	-1.4	-7	-0.05	4.48	-13.8	8.9	116681	12487
2016	1	24	15:30	1.4	-0.1	-0.1	0.3	-1	-0.04	4.52	-13.8	10.3	116682	12487
2016	1	24	18:30	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	0.2	-7	-0.06	4.50	-13.9	9.8	116683	12487
2016	1	24	22:00	1.3	-0.2	-0.1	-0.6	-12	-0.06	4.46	-13.8	13.8	116684	12487
2016	1	25	4:00	1.2	-0.1	-0.1	1.7	2	-0.05	4.37	-13.9	12.9	116686	12487
2016	1	25	7:30	1.1	-0.1	-0.1	-1.2	-4	-0.06	4.23	-14.0	10.6	116687	12487
2016	1	25	12:00	1.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-13	-0.09	4.20	-13.8	21.5	116688	12487
2016	1	25	16:00	0.9	-0.2	-0.1	-2.1	-11	-0.08	4.17	-13.8	23.7	116689	12487
2016	1	25	21:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.9	-4	-0.05	4.11	-13.8	26.5	116690	12487
2016	1	26	0:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-1.7	-8	-0.08	4.06	-13.8	28.1	116691	12487
2016	1	26	11:19	3.7	-2.3	-2.4	1.8	-4	-0.19	6.58	1.5	13.1	116694	12488
2016	1	26	15:00	3.7	-1.9	-1.9	1.1	-6	-0.15	6.72	1.7	22.9	116695	12488
2016	1	26	19:25	3.7	-1.9	-1.9	0.7	-23	-0.15	6.75	1.7	25.4	116697	12488
2016	1	26	23:00	3.6	-1.9	-1.9	2.5	-5	-0.15	6.72	1.7	27.4	116698	12488
2016	1	27	12:00	3.8	-0.9	-0.9	-0.8	3	-0.08	6.44	1.0	16.6	116700	12488
2016	1	27	18:07	3.5	-0.9	-0.9	-0.0	-6	-0.08	6.59	1.0	24.7	116702	12488
2016	1	30	12:16	1.7	-0.2	-0.2	2.9	3	-0.04	4.83	8.9	5.1	116715	12489
2016	1	30	15:35	4.6	-1.8	-1.8	0.0	-50	-0.10	7.40	8.9	6.9	116716	12489
2016	1	30	18:15	4.5	-1.7	-1.7	-0.2	-35	-0.10	7.32	8.8	6.8	116717	12489
2016	1	31	0:00	4.5	-2.3	-2.3	0.8	-43	-0.14	7.45	8.8	10.6	116718	12489
2016	1	31	6:15	4.2	-1.9	-1.9	1.2	-34	-0.12	7.28	8.9	15.1	116719	12489
2016	1	31	10:01	4.1	-1.6	-1.6	1.1	-36	-0.11	7.17	8.9	17.2	116721	12489
2016	1	31	15:00	4.0	-1.6	-1.6	0.4	-48	-0.11	7.11	8.9	19.9	116722	12489

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	1	31	18:17	4.0	-1.6	-1.6	0.1	-52	-0.11	7.13	8.6	11.0	116723	12489
2016	2	1	0:00	3.7	-1.4	-1.4	-1.0	-45	-0.10	7.15	8.6	18.2	116724	12489
2016	2	1	18:36	3.2	-1.0	-1.0	0.6	-51	-0.10	6.67	8.3	23.7	116728	12489
2016	2	2	0:00	3.0	-0.7	-0.7	1.9	-38	-0.07	6.58	8.0	21.1	116729	12489
2016	2	3	6:23	1.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.5	-15	-0.09	5.04	-0.7	-20.6	116732	12491
2016	2	4	18:30	1.3	-0.1	-0.1	-0.0	5	-0.03	3.90	0.5	-21.8	116735	12491
2016	2	10	3:40	5.2	1.0	1.1	5.9	-24	0.07	5.88	11.7	-13.0	116749	12497
2016	2	10	7:00	5.4	0.9	1.0	6.4	-9	0.06	5.79	11.8	-13.1	116750	12497
2016	2	10	10:05	5.5	0.8	0.9	7.8	33	0.05	5.68	12.1	-18.9	116751	12497
2016	2	10	12:45	5.7	0.7	0.7	1.3	-1	0.04	5.54	12.1	-17.4	116752	12497
2016	2	10	15:45	5.5	0.6	0.6	5.2	49	0.04	5.61	12.1	-15.7	116753	12497
2016	2	10	18:47	5.5	0.4	0.4	2.1	71	0.03	5.59	12.0	-10.6	116754	12497
2016	2	10	22:00	5.4	0.4	0.3	1.0	63	0.03	5.44	12.1	-12.3	116755	12497
2016	2	11	0:54	4.7	-0.1	-0.1	4.3	37	-0.01	5.43	12.1	-10.7	116756	12497
2016	2	11	4:15	4.5	0.8	0.8	6.1	88	0.07	5.32	12.1	-8.8	116757	12497
2016	2	11	7:30	4.4	0.7	0.7	5.9	83	0.06	5.21	12.0	-7.0	116758	12497
2016	2	11	9:05	4.0	-0.2	-0.2	0.5	5	-0.02	5.25	12.1	-6.1	116759	12497
2016	2	11	19:22	3.5	-0.8	-0.8	13.2	47	-0.09	5.04	12.1	-0.4	116762	12497
2016	2	11	22:40	3.3	-2.9	-2.8	-3.5	-163	-0.34	5.08	12.1	1.4	116763	12497
2016	2	12	1:35	3.5	-2.9	-2.8	0.1	-205	-0.36	4.57	12.1	3.0	116764	12497
2016	2	12	19:58	4.5	-2.2	-2.0	-3.3	-223	-0.24	3.89	12.1	13.2	116765	12497
2016	2	12	23:10	4.8	-1.6	-1.5	0.5	-164	-0.18	3.74	12.0	11.6	116766	12497
2016	2	13	2:10	4.8	-1.6	-1.4	0.6	-195	-0.18	3.74	12.1	16.6	116767	12497
2016	2	13	7:00	5.1	-1.2	-1.1	-3.1	-201	-0.13	3.64	12.1	19.3	116768	12497
2016	3	5	17:03	1.3	0.1	0.1	2.1	10	0.03	3.46	3.9	-25.4	116825	12510
2016	3	12	16:04	1.5	0.1	0.1	1.2	12	0.02	4.28	2.3	-20.7	116876	12519
2016	3	15	15:04	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.2	2	0.00	4.86	3.5	0.1	116886	12519
2016	3	15	19:20	1.9	0.1	0.1	0.4	9	0.02	4.92	3.5	2.5	116888	12519
2016	3	15	23:20	1.9	-0.0	-0.0	2.3	12	-0.00	4.95	3.5	4.7	116889	12519
2016	3	16	3:04	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	0.4	1	-0.01	4.78	3.5	6.8	116891	12519
2016	3	16	7:04	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	0.6	2	-0.02	4.82	3.5	9.0	116892	12519
2016	3	16	11:04	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	3.0	27	-0.01	4.56	3.5	11.2	116893	12519
2016	3	20	6:08	1.8	-0.0	-0.0	0.1	19	-0.01	5.37	12.6	-20.0	116908	12524

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	4	2	22:00	2.8	0.3	0.2	3.4	38	0.03	6.21	-6.4	24.1	116988	12526
2016	4	3	16:00	2.1	-0.0	-0.0	1.5	18	-0.00	5.71	-7.0	27.1	116994	12526
2016	4	5	15:30	1.5	0.7	0.6	9.8	122	0.30	3.07	5.5	16.1	117004	12528
2016	4	5	17:04	1.4	0.6	0.6	0.4	53	0.30	2.95	5.5	17.0	117005	12528
2016	4	5	19:00	1.5	0.7	0.7	2.4	78	0.33	2.99	5.5	18.0	117006	12528
2016	4	5	20:53	1.5	0.7	0.7	4.2	66	0.31	2.99	5.5	19.6	117007	12528
2016	4	5	23:30	1.7	0.8	0.8	4.9	103	0.33	3.00	5.3	14.1	117008	12528
2016	4	6	1:20	1.7	0.7	0.7	5.9	78	0.28	3.07	5.5	21.6	117009	12528
2016	4	6	4:15	1.7	0.8	0.7	2.4	62	0.30	3.06	5.5	23.2	117010	12528
2016	4	6	6:14	1.3	0.6	0.5	6.4	94	0.29	2.84	5.2	15.8	117011	12528
2016	4	6	11:04	1.6	0.7	0.7	10.4	97	0.27	3.14	5.0	15.0	117013	12528
2016	4	7	0:00	1.2	0.3	0.3	3.4	41	0.17	3.05	4.7	19.4	117018	12528
2016	4	7	3:20	1.1	0.3	0.3	3.1	36	0.17	2.99	4.6	17.4	117019	12528
2016	4	10	18:34	11.5	-4.7	-4.7	8.2	-20	-0.08	9.98	8.0	-24.1	117052	12529
2016	4	11	12:05	13.3	-11.3	-11.2	-6.6	-152	-0.16	10.62	8.8	-25.1	117055	12529
2016	4	12	0:05	15.7	-2.5	-2.6	6.7	53	-0.03	10.04	8.8	-15.8	117058	12529
2016	4	12	12:35	14.9	-13.8	-13.8	-5.1	-155	-0.17	10.95	9.4	-22.6	117063	12529
2016	4	13	18:32	17.3	-13.0	-13.0	8.6	-83	-0.13	11.15	9.4	-5.9	117076	12529
2016	4	14	2:21	18.1	-12.6	-12.6	4.4	-95	-0.12	11.15	9.4	-1.6	117079	12529
2016	4	14	12:45	18.1	-9.3	-9.3	5.4	-29	-0.09	11.10	9.4	4.2	117084	12529
2016	4	14	18:15	14.2	-5.4	-5.4	5.9	15	-0.08	9.98	9.4	7.2	117087	12529
2016	4	16	3:15	15.7	-13.5	-13.4	-1.2	-164	-0.17	10.29	9.0	14.3	117094	12529
2016	4	16	22:00	13.3	-10.6	-10.6	3.3	-74	-0.17	9.25	9.2	23.0	117099	12529
2016	4	24	14:04	2.3	0.3	0.3	1.9	41	0.05	5.56	-3.6	-24.2	117138	12533
2016	4	24	15:05	2.3	0.3	0.3	-0.4	36	0.05	5.56	-3.9	-13.4	117139	12533
2016	4	25	13:43	2.5	0.5	0.5	-0.3	38	0.07	5.80	-3.6	-11.1	117140	12533
2016	4	25	14:35	2.5	0.6	0.6	-1.0	44	0.08	5.73	-3.6	-10.6	117141	12533
2016	4	25	15:40	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.8	39	0.07	5.75	-3.6	-10.0	117142	12533
2016	4	29	14:45	2.8	1.9	1.8	1.5	88	0.24	5.65	13.7	-13.5	117159	12536
2016	4	29	19:47	2.9	1.8	1.7	5.7	104	0.22	5.70	13.9	-19.7	117160	12536
2016	4	30	0:25	3.2	2.0	1.9	4.9	105	0.22	5.65	13.9	-17.1	117161	12536
2016	4	30	5:13	3.4	1.9	1.8	7.6	104	0.20	5.55	13.8	-11.1	117162	12536
2016	4	30	9:01	3.6	1.9	1.8	7.5	101	0.19	5.48	13.9	-12.4	117163	12536

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	4	30	13:00	1.0	-0.2	-0.2	-2.1	-24	-0.16	2.69	4.0	2.8	117164	12535
2016	4	30	17:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.4	-6	-0.11	2.72	4.0	4.9	117165	12535
2016	4	30	22:01	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-0.7	-10	-0.11	2.65	4.0	7.8	117170	12535
2016	5	1	1:45	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.2	-10	-0.13	2.53	4.0	9.9	117171	12535
2016	5	1	6:00	0.7	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	-16	-0.16	2.60	4.0	12.2	117172	12535
2016	5	1	9:45	0.7	-0.1	-0.1	0.2	-7	-0.11	2.61	4.0	14.3	117173	12535
2016	5	1	14:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	1.0	-10	-0.12	2.60	4.0	16.7	117174	12535
2016	5	1	19:00	1.6	-0.2	-0.2	1.6	-48	-0.08	3.44	14.9	-15.3	117176	12539
2016	5	1	22:30	0.8	-0.2	-0.2	-0.9	-11	-0.19	2.92	4.0	21.4	117177	12535
2016	5	2	1:30	0.9	-0.2	-0.1	1.9	-2	-0.13	2.84	3.7	11.4	117178	12535
2016	5	2	5:15	0.8	-0.2	-0.2	1.3	-1	-0.17	2.96	4.0	25.2	117179	12535
2016	5	2	9:45	0.8	-0.2	-0.2	-0.8	-14	-0.18	2.94	4.0	27.7	117180	12535
2016	5	2	17:35	1.6	-0.0	-0.0	-2.8	-17	-0.01	3.27	15.3	-16.9	117184	12539
2016	5	2	19:30	1.7	-0.0	-0.0	1.1	-14	-0.01	3.18	15.3	-15.9	117185	12539
2016	5	3	2:15	0.9	-0.3	-0.3	-0.7	-15	-0.23	2.98	3.4	20.7	117187	12535
2016	5	3	17:27	1.4	0.0	0.0	3.1	9	0.01	3.39	14.5	-1.8	117192	12539
2016	5	3	19:24	1.5	-0.0	-0.0	6.5	20	-0.01	3.42	14.5	-0.7	117193	12539
2016	5	3	22:30	1.3	0.0	0.0	7.4	30	0.01	3.23	14.5	0.8	117194	12539
2016	5	4	1:45	1.1	-0.0	-0.0	2.5	1	-0.02	3.06	14.6	2.5	117195	12539
2016	5	4	8:00	1.1	-0.0	-0.0	0.2	8	-0.02	3.05	14.5	5.4	117197	12539
2016	5	4	11:00	1.1	-0.0	-0.0	5.3	21	-0.01	3.02	14.6	7.6	117198	12539
2016	5	4	17:24	1.3	0.0	0.0	6.0	39	0.01	2.91	14.5	7.2	117200	12539
2016	5	4	19:24	1.2	-0.1	-0.1	3.5	27	-0.03	2.98	14.5	12.6	117201	12539
2016	5	5	3:45	1.1	0.1	0.1	4.2	25	0.04	3.03	14.5	16.9	117203	12539
2016	5	5	8:15	1.0	0.1	0.1	3.3	26	0.05	2.90	14.5	19.4	117204	12539
2016	5	5	17:04	0.9	0.0	0.0	3.6	23	0.01	2.91	14.3	15.8	117207	12539
2016	5	5	19:04	0.9	0.0	0.0	1.6	11	0.02	3.00	14.3	15.1	117208	12539
2016	5	6	7:32	1.5	0.1	0.1	-2.1	1	0.02	4.62	1.0	-24.8	117212	12541
2016	5	8	6:48	2.5	0.1	0.1	0.2	9	0.02	5.99	9.5	-28.1	117228	12542
2016	5	8	11:44	2.6	0.1	0.1	3.8	23	0.01	5.78	9.2	-13.4	117229	12542
2016	5	8	16:58	2.6	0.1	0.1	2.9	13	0.01	5.69	9.5	-22.4	117230	12542
2016	5	8	23:23	2.8	-0.0	-0.1	3.3	29	-0.00	5.37	9.5	-18.9	117231	12542
2016	5	9	2:30	2.9	-0.1	-0.1	4.7	25	-0.02	5.22	9.5	-17.1	117232	12542

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	5	9	6:14	3.1	-0.5	-0.5	2.1	3	-0.06	5.18	9.5	-15.1	117233	12542
2016	5	9	21:00	3.7	-0.8	-0.7	1.6	-59	-0.09	4.82	2.5	-3.5	117236	12542
2016	5	10	3:06	3.7	-1.0	-1.0	2.8	-42	-0.11	4.82	9.5	-3.5	117237	12542
2016	5	10	8:01	3.6	-0.8	-0.8	1.6	-11	-0.09	4.79	9.5	-0.8	117238	12542
2016	5	13	18:19	2.5	-1.1	-1.1	-0.3	-10	-0.16	5.47	7.9	24.3	117303	12542
2016	5	13	21:29	2.5	-1.1	-1.0	-1.6	-21	-0.16	5.36	7.6	24.5	117305	12542
2016	5	14	7:09	2.0	-0.7	-0.6	0.4	-15	-0.12	5.24	7.6	25.5	117311	12542
2016	5	19	18:51	13.4	12.0	12.0	2.2	266	0.19	9.53	-9.9	-10.0	117349	12546
2016	5	19	20:29	13.4	12.6	12.5	12.3	308	0.20	9.49	-9.9	-9.1	117350	12546
2016	5	19	22:07	13.5	13.3	13.2	10.8	314	0.21	9.47	-9.9	-4.2	117351	12546
2016	5	20	1:25	13.5	13.4	13.4	18.0	354	0.21	9.44	-9.9	-6.3	117353	12546
2016	5	20	3:03	13.8	14.2	14.1	11.9	326	0.21	9.54	-9.9	-5.5	117354	12546
2016	5	20	4:41	14.1	14.5	14.5	11.6	318	0.22	9.56	-9.9	-4.5	117355	12546
2016	5	20	7:58	14.2	15.5	15.5	19.4	351	0.23	9.61	-9.9	-1.4	117356	12546
2016	5	20	12:53	13.7	14.3	14.3	9.3	277	0.22	9.61	-9.9	-0.0	117359	12546
2016	5	20	14:31	14.1	14.6	14.6	5.9	245	0.21	9.73	-9.9	0.9	117360	12546
2016	5	20	16:10	14.0	14.2	14.2	7.6	238	0.21	9.78	-9.9	1.8	117361	12546
2016	5	22	13:37	6.8	6.7	6.5	35.7	536	0.26	7.58	-10.2	26.6	117374	12546
2016	5	22	18:40	11.6	11.8	11.8	10.2	251	0.22	9.23	-10.3	28.6	117375	12546
2016	5	23	1:07	11.1	12.3	12.2	13.4	279	0.24	8.99	-10.4	18.1	117376	12546
2016	5	23	16:02	9.0	9.2	9.1	8.2	209	0.24	8.57	-10.5	20.3	117381	12546
2016	5	24	23:04	2.3	0.4	0.4	-3.0	-9	0.06	5.64	-10.8	26.7	117398	12546
2016	5	27	20:26	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	2.0	-3	-0.02	4.75	11.9	22.3	117423	12548
2016	5	28	11:01	1.7	-0.1	-0.1	0.7	-5	-0.01	4.99	10.2	25.7	117431	12548
2016	5	28	12:14	1.7	-0.1	-0.1	1.1	0	-0.01	4.97	10.2	27.2	117432	12548
2016	6	14	11:21	4.7	4.5	4.4	3.1	105	0.23	8.03	-9.0	-16.9	117590	12553
2016	6	14	12:30	4.1	3.8	3.7	4.3	115	0.24	7.50	-9.1	-25.7	117591	12553
2016	6	14	16:00	4.8	4.5	4.5	3.9	109	0.23	8.14	-9.1	-23.8	117592	12553
2016	6	15	0:04	5.3	5.6	5.6	10.1	169	0.26	8.03	-9.1	-19.3	117593	12553
2016	6	15	3:15	5.3	5.8	5.8	13.8	174	0.27	8.04	-8.9	-12.9	117594	12553
2016	6	15	16:31	5.8	6.3	6.3	8.3	153	0.27	8.06	-9.1	-10.2	117596	12553
2016	6	16	0:35	5.8	5.7	5.6	12.7	159	0.24	8.07	-9.1	-5.7	117602	12553
2016	6	16	3:51	5.8	5.4	5.4	6.7	126	0.23	8.14	-9.1	-3.9	117603	12553

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	6	16	7:14	5.8	5.3	5.2	7.4	126	0.22	8.12	-9.1	-2.1	117605	12553
2016	6	16	12:04	5.8	5.3	5.2	6.9	114	0.22	8.08	-9.0	0.5	117607	12553
2016	6	16	15:19	5.7	5.2	5.2	7.1	124	0.22	8.28	-9.1	2.4	117608	12553
2016	6	16	17:08	5.6	5.0	5.0	1.9	108	0.21	8.26	-9.1	3.4	117609	12553
2016	6	16	20:30	5.5	5.0	5.0	3.1	110	0.23	8.13	-9.1	5.3	117610	12553
2016	6	17	1:01	5.4	5.0	5.0	5.0	106	0.23	8.16	-9.1	7.8	117612	12553
2016	6	17	4:26	5.3	4.9	4.9	2.8	104	0.22	8.24	-9.1	9.7	117613	12553
2016	6	17	7:43	5.3	4.5	4.5	7.6	112	0.21	8.12	-9.0	8.0	117614	12553
2016	6	17	12:39	5.1	4.4	4.4	3.5	94	0.21	8.01	-9.1	14.2	117616	12553
2016	6	17	16:10	5.1	4.3	4.3	7.2	107	0.21	8.04	-9.0	10.9	117617	12553
2016	6	18	0:07	4.8	3.6	3.6	4.6	90	0.19	7.97	-9.1	20.6	117618	12553
2016	6	18	8:20	4.1	2.9	2.9	2.8	88	0.20	7.28	-9.1	25.1	117620	12553
2016	6	18	11:36	4.2	3.0	3.0	3.9	84	0.19	7.45	-9.1	26.9	117622	12553
2016	6	18	14:52	4.3	3.2	3.2	2.6	75	0.19	7.53	-8.9	16.5	117623	12553
2016	6	19	15:29	3.2	2.0	2.0	2.1	49	0.17	7.19	-8.5	20.1	117629	12553
2016	6	19	23:40	2.9	1.5	1.5	3.1	42	0.14	7.03	-8.6	21.6	117631	12553
2016	6	21	10:05	0.7	-0.0	-0.0	-1.2	-8	-0.03	3.12	3.7	-27.6	117640	12556
2016	6	21	12:05	0.7	-0.0	-0.0	-1.2	-3	-0.00	3.13	3.7	-26.5	117641	12556
2016	6	21	15:15	0.7	-0.0	-0.0	-0.4	-1	-0.03	3.12	3.7	-24.8	117642	12556
2016	6	21	17:01	0.7	-0.0	-0.0	-1.2	-4	-0.01	2.98	3.7	-23.8	117643	12556
2016	6	22	9:10	0.5	-0.0	-0.0	0.0	-1	-0.01	2.92	3.7	-14.8	117651	12556
2016	7	10	6:49	1.7	-0.8	-0.7	2.4	-17	-0.16	5.70	7.5	-28.6	117819	12564
2016	7	10	20:21	1.6	-0.7	-0.7	0.7	-33	-0.17	5.38	7.2	-24.4	117826	12564
2016	7	10	23:06	1.6	-0.7	-0.7	-0.9	-38	-0.17	5.32	7.2	-24.7	117827	12564
2016	7	13	5:46	1.3	0.1	0.1	2.1	32	0.03	4.20	6.2	-22.1	117847	12564
2016	7	19	11:56	7.0	-0.0	-0.1	17.0	126	-0.00	7.39	0.5	11.1	117899	12567
2016	7	19	13:32	6.0	-5.6	-5.5	1.0	-113	-0.24	7.68	0.3	22.4	117900	12567
2016	7	19	16:42	10.3	-4.7	-4.7	3.6	-87	-0.12	7.48	0.5	18.3	117902	12567
2016	7	19	21:56	10.4	-3.9	-3.8	-0.2	-124	-0.11	6.91	0.3	27.0	117905	12567
2016	7	19	23:30	10.7	-5.1	-5.0	-1.8	-143	-0.13	7.49	0.3	27.9	117906	12567
2016	7	21	1:40	9.5	-1.2	-1.1	1.3	-85	-0.04	6.99	1.1	23.6	117917	12567
2016	7	22	23:35	2.6	-0.6	-0.5	-7.6	-109	-0.12	3.76	3.5	27.8	117934	12567
2016	8	9	19:35	3.3	-0.5	-0.5	2.7	-20	-0.06	5.46	5.8	-26.6	118105	12573

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	8	10	6:45	2.9	-0.5	-0.5	0.3	-20	-0.06	5.13	5.3	-26.1	118112	12573
2016	8	11	19:15	3.5	0.0	0.1	-1.9	-5	0.00	5.45	3.2	-27.6	118124	12573
2016	8	12	1:19	3.4	-0.0	-0.0	-2.8	-2	-0.00	5.33	3.7	-12.2	118125	12573
2016	8	12	6:34	3.4	-0.1	-0.1	0.5	8	-0.01	5.76	3.5	-15.6	118126	12573
2016	8	12	13:00	3.6	-0.0	-0.0	1.6	1	-0.00	5.44	3.4	-11.8	118127	12573
2016	8	12	18:20	3.5	0.1	0.1	2.3	10	0.01	5.57	4.0	-16.0	118128	12573
2016	8	13	0:30	3.6	-0.0	-0.0	1.8	4	-0.00	5.50	3.9	-15.8	118129	12573
2016	8	13	3:31	3.6	0.2	0.2	-1.5	-3	0.02	5.49	4.0	-8.6	118130	12573
2016	8	13	6:45	3.4	0.2	0.2	2.9	27	0.02	5.56	3.9	-12.4	118131	12573
2016	8	13	12:00	3.6	0.2	0.2	1.5	6	0.02	5.55	3.9	-9.4	118132	12573
2016	8	13	15:18	3.5	0.2	0.2	1.7	7	0.02	5.36	3.9	-7.6	118133	12573
2016	8	13	20:18	3.6	0.2	0.3	1.5	16	0.02	5.35	3.9	-4.8	118134	12573
2016	8	14	1:00	3.7	0.3	0.3	1.8	11	0.03	5.30	3.9	-2.2	118135	12573
2016	8	14	6:14	3.6	0.3	0.3	-0.1	22	0.03	5.40	3.9	0.7	118136	12573
2016	8	14	9:00	3.4	0.4	0.3	2.3	39	0.04	5.15	3.9	2.2	118137	12573
2016	8	14	12:00	3.4	0.5	0.5	6.8	52	0.05	5.41	3.9	3.9	118138	12573
2016	8	14	14:45	3.3	0.3	0.3	4.8	17	0.03	5.46	3.9	5.4	118139	12573
2016	8	14	18:00	3.3	0.3	0.3	2.1	5	0.03	5.43	4.0	4.4	118140	12573
2016	8	14	22:30	3.3	0.4	0.4	2.8	17	0.05	5.30	3.9	9.8	118141	12573
2016	8	15	1:27	2.8	0.5	0.4	8.9	75	0.06	5.11	3.9	11.4	118142	12573
2016	8	15	6:18	3.1	0.3	0.4	6.6	24	0.04	5.20	4.1	7.3	118143	12573
2016	8	15	10:01	3.0	0.2	0.2	3.4	23	0.03	4.81	3.9	16.4	118144	12573
2016	8	15	13:00	2.9	0.3	0.3	6.9	29	0.04	5.04	3.9	17.8	118145	12573
2016	8	15	17:00	2.6	0.4	0.4	7.4	54	0.07	4.78	3.9	20.0	118146	12573
2016	8	15	21:28	2.8	0.2	0.2	5.3	26	0.03	4.93	4.2	16.2	118147	12573
2016	8	16	0:40	2.7	0.2	0.2	3.2	27	0.03	4.81	3.9	24.3	118148	12573
2016	8	16	3:39	2.6	0.3	0.3	0.8	15	0.04	4.79	3.9	26.0	118149	12573
2016	8	24	7:26	2.3	-1.8	-1.8	0.9	-27	-0.26	5.92	11.0	-1.2	118207	12579
2016	8	25	7:20	1.6	-1.1	-1.1	0.8	-19	-0.27	5.04	11.1	9.3	118210	12579
2016	8	27	20:30	0.7	0.1	0.1	1.4	22	0.08	2.84	-19.2	0.6	118243	12580
2016	8	28	8:05	2.5	-1.0	-1.0	3.8	7	-0.13	6.03	9.5	-3.4	118244	12581
2016	8	28	18:15	0.8	0.1	0.1	0.7	16	0.09	3.04	-19.2	12.4	118247	12580
2016	8	28	19:25	0.8	0.1	0.1	2.7	14	0.07	3.08	-19.0	9.0	118248	12580

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	8	29	0:04	1.1	0.1	0.1	-1.1	14	0.06	2.79	-19.2	15.5	118249	12580
2016	8	29	1:35	1.1	0.1	0.1	-0.8	8	0.08	2.83	-19.2	16.3	118250	12580
2016	8	29	8:05	2.6	-0.4	-0.4	2.8	10	-0.05	5.80	9.5	9.9	118251	12579
2016	8	29	18:34	0.7	-0.0	-0.0	1.5	-4	-0.02	3.11	-19.2	25.6	118256	12580
2016	8	29	20:00	0.7	-0.0	-0.0	-0.9	-9	-0.04	3.11	-19.2	26.4	118257	12580
2016	8	30	7:35	1.8	-0.0	-0.0	-2.2	-11	-0.01	5.15	9.5	22.9	118258	12579
2016	9	1	0:21	1.2	0.1	0.1	0.3	2	0.03	5.12	12.1	22.7	118267	12579
2016	9	13	0:05	1.3	-0.1	-0.1	3.7	16	-0.02	4.26	3.3	7.1	118366	12581
2016	9	13	2:15	1.5	-0.1	-0.1	4.4	17	-0.02	4.40	3.3	9.2	118369	12581
2016	9	13	2:50	1.5	-0.1	-0.1	2.1	13	-0.02	4.37	3.3	9.9	118370	12581
2016	9	13	3:55	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	4.8	27	-0.04	4.33	3.3	10.5	118371	12581
2016	9	13	4:30	1.5	-0.1	-0.1	4.0	17	-0.02	4.27	3.3	10.8	118372	12581
2016	9	13	5:30	1.2	-0.0	-0.0	4.7	15	-0.01	4.30	3.3	10.4	118373	12581
2016	9	13	6:12	1.5	-0.0	-0.0	2.8	15	-0.01	4.40	3.4	6.3	118374	12581
2016	9	13	7:06	1.4	-0.0	-0.0	3.6	31	-0.01	4.42	3.3	12.2	118375	12581
2016	9	13	7:40	1.5	-0.1	-0.1	4.6	24	-0.02	4.45	3.3	12.6	118376	12581
2016	9	13	8:45	1.5	-0.0	-0.0	5.0	25	-0.00	4.41	3.3	13.2	118377	12581
2016	9	13	17:26	1.2	0.0	0.0	2.4	23	0.01	4.41	3.3	18.0	118380	12581
2016	9	18	16:00	1.3	0.0	0.0	-0.4	-6	0.02	3.12	12.1	-16.0	118422	12592
2016	9	19	0:04	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.4	0	0.01	2.95	11.3	-27.1	118423	12592
2016	9	19	1:00	1.1	0.0	0.0	-1.1	-10	0.01	3.00	11.3	-26.6	118424	12592
2016	9	27	12:15	0.9	-0.0	-0.0	-0.3	1	-0.00	6.49	-13.7	23.6	118523	12597
2016	10	6	18:11	5.0	1.1	1.1	10.9	116	0.06	7.53	-16.4	-24.8	118612	12599
2016	10	7	7:01	4.4	0.5	0.5	9.5	77	0.03	7.61	-16.7	-21.8	118616	12599
2016	10	7	16:52	4.9	0.7	0.7	7.8	85	0.04	7.63	-16.9	-18.1	118619	12599
2016	10	7	20:07	2.2	0.1	0.0	1.1	25	0.01	4.31	11.5	6.4	118622	12598
2016	10	7	23:40	2.7	0.2	0.2	0.9	29	0.03	4.24	11.5	5.4	118623	12598
2016	10	8	4:12	3.0	0.5	0.5	3.1	63	0.08	4.27	11.5	10.9	118624	12598
2016	10	8	9:01	4.8	0.2	0.1	12.1	72	0.01	7.30	-17.4	-18.6	118626	12599
2016	10	9	9:30	4.9	1.0	1.0	3.5	67	0.06	7.20	-16.9	-1.6	118634	12599
2016	10	9	12:30	4.6	1.1	1.1	4.9	72	0.07	7.24	-16.9	-0.5	118635	12599
2016	10	9	14:36	4.5	1.4	1.4	0.3	58	0.08	7.30	-16.9	0.7	118636	12599
2016	10	9	18:16	4.3	1.4	1.4	4.3	63	0.09	7.22	-16.9	2.7	118637	12599

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	10	9	21:16	4.2	1.4	1.3	4.4	59	0.09	7.24	-16.9	4.3	118638	12599
2016	10	10	3:28	4.0	1.3	1.3	5.0	51	0.09	7.33	-16.9	7.7	118641	12599
2016	10	10	8:21	4.0	1.5	1.5	5.7	73	0.10	7.11	-16.9	10.4	118643	12599
2016	10	10	18:39	3.9	1.2	1.2	1.3	32	0.09	6.82	-16.9	16.0	118646	12599
2016	10	11	14:40	3.6	1.4	1.4	-4.2	14	0.12	6.48	-16.9	27.0	118648	12599
2016	10	11	16:00	3.9	1.4	1.4	4.4	42	0.11	6.65	-16.4	18.1	118649	12599
2016	10	11	19:21	3.5	1.1	1.1	0.8	22	0.10	6.52	-16.3	18.1	118651	12599
2016	10	15	10:29	1.1	-0.1	-0.1	1.9	0	-0.06	3.69	5.2	-18.7	118689	12602
2016	10	15	18:32	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-6	-0.04	3.74	5.2	-10.4	118690	12602
2016	10	16	2:08	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	1.2	4	-0.06	3.64	5.0	-14.3	118691	12602
2016	10	16	7:00	1.0	0.0	0.0	-0.8	-12	0.00	3.58	5.0	-11.6	118692	12602
2016	10	16	12:26	1.0	0.1	0.1	-0.9	-3	0.03	3.61	3.5	-8.1	118696	12602
2016	10	16	15:35	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.6	3	0.01	3.56	5.0	-6.8	118701	12602
2016	10	16	18:55	1.1	0.1	0.1	1.8	7	0.02	3.49	5.0	-4.9	118702	12602
2016	10	16	23:39	1.1	0.1	0.1	1.7	6	0.04	3.55	5.1	-2.3	118703	12602
2016	10	17	2:43	1.0	0.1	0.1	4.7	28	0.04	3.27	5.0	-0.6	118704	12602
2016	10	17	6:01	1.1	0.1	0.1	1.0	5	0.05	3.36	5.0	1.2	118705	12602
2016	10	17	9:11	1.1	0.1	0.1	2.3	11	0.07	3.34	5.0	3.0	118706	12602
2016	10	17	12:11	1.2	0.2	0.2	1.1	15	0.09	3.38	5.0	4.7	118707	12602
2016	10	17	16:17	1.1	0.1	0.1	1.8	20	0.07	3.43	5.0	7.0	118708	12602
2016	10	17	19:30	1.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	12	0.03	3.49	5.0	8.7	118709	12602
2016	10	17	22:43	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.4	-5	0.02	3.47	5.0	10.5	118710	12602
2016	10	18	18:29	1.4	-0.1	-0.2	-1.4	7	-0.05	4.10	4.8	21.7	118713	12602
2016	10	19	3:54	1.4	-0.2	-0.2	0.9	11	-0.08	4.15	4.8	26.9	118715	12602
2016	10	25	6:14	1.2	-0.3	-0.3	-0.1	-18	-0.12	3.99	12.2	19.9	118742	12603
2016	10	28	9:02	1.0	-0.1	-0.1	3.2	23	-0.05	2.87	5.1	0.6	118757	12604
2016	10	29	10:02	0.8	-0.0	-0.0	2.0	8	-0.02	3.63	4.0	12.1	118766	12604
2016	11	3	14:41	0.5	-0.0	-0.0	1.7	4	-0.06	2.50	6.1	12.2	118792	12604
2016	11	16	0:01	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	4.0	0	-0.09	3.45	12.8	10.0	118875	12610
2016	11	16	1:00	1.3	-0.3	-0.2	1.9	-11	-0.11	3.60	12.8	10.5	118876	12610
2016	11	16	2:26	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	5.6	1	-0.09	3.62	12.8	11.3	118877	12610
2016	11	16	4:03	1.4	-0.3	-0.3	4.0	1	-0.12	3.70	12.8	12.2	118878	12610
2016	11	16	21:04	1.3	-0.3	-0.3	0.9	-8	-0.12	4.47	12.9	13.3	118885	12610

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	11	17	0:26	1.2	-0.4	-0.3	-0.6	-16	-0.13	4.63	12.8	23.5	118887	12610
2016	11	17	2:00	1.1	-0.4	-0.4	-0.7	-16	-0.14	4.67	12.8	24.3	118888	12610
2016	11	17	3:35	1.1	-0.3	-0.3	-1.7	-18	-0.14	4.54	12.8	25.2	118889	12610
2016	11	17	5:01	1.1	-0.3	-0.3	1.4	-13	-0.13	4.56	12.8	26.0	118890	12610
2016	11	17	6:38	1.1	-0.4	-0.4	-0.1	-25	-0.16	4.54	13.0	14.3	118891	12610
2016	11	17	8:38	1.0	-0.4	-0.4	-0.0	-23	-0.15	4.66	12.8	28.0	118892	12610
2016	11	17	10:55	1.3	-0.4	-0.4	-2.1	-8	-0.12	4.74	12.7	26.6	118893	12610
2016	11	17	11:30	1.3	-0.3	-0.3	0.7	4	-0.10	4.71	12.9	13.6	118894	12610
2016	11	17	12:05	1.3	-0.3	-0.3	1.9	11	-0.09	4.67	12.7	27.3	118895	12610
2016	11	17	12:40	1.3	-0.2	-0.2	1.5	1	-0.08	4.56	12.7	27.6	118896	12610
2016	11	17	13:30	1.3	-0.3	-0.3	-1.4	0	-0.09	4.47	12.7	28.1	118897	12610
2016	11	27	19:10	3.8	-0.0	0.0	1.3	-16	-0.00	6.41	6.0	-24.2	118962	12612
2016	11	27	23:51	3.8	-0.2	-0.2	-2.7	-25	-0.01	6.42	6.0	-21.6	118963	12612
2016	11	28	4:35	3.8	0.0	0.0	0.5	-13	0.00	6.37	6.0	-19.0	118964	12612
2016	11	28	9:26	3.6	-0.1	-0.1	0.3	-15	-0.01	6.44	6.0	-16.3	118966	12612
2016	11	28	14:44	3.7	-0.2	-0.1	0.6	-18	-0.01	6.42	6.0	-13.4	118968	12612
2016	11	28	21:22	3.7	-0.3	-0.3	0.5	-32	-0.03	6.19	6.0	-8.0	118969	12612
2016	11	29	3:33	3.6	-0.3	-0.3	1.8	-13	-0.03	6.06	6.0	-6.2	118970	12612
2016	11	29	6:47	3.4	-0.2	-0.2	-2.1	-34	-0.02	6.05	6.0	-4.4	118971	12612
2016	11	29	10:00	3.4	-0.5	-0.5	0.2	-34	-0.05	5.80	7.5	0.5	118972	12612
2016	11	29	12:00	3.3	-0.4	-0.4	-3.1	-28	-0.04	5.99	7.5	1.4	118973	12612
2016	11	29	14:00	3.3	-0.4	-0.4	3.5	-13	-0.04	5.86	7.5	2.5	118974	12612
2016	11	29	16:00	3.3	-0.5	-0.5	3.2	-14	-0.05	5.89	7.5	3.6	118975	12612
2016	11	29	19:01	2.8	-0.2	-0.2	6.6	11	-0.03	5.47	7.5	3.8	118977	12612
2016	11	29	22:00	3.2	-0.5	-0.5	5.7	7	-0.05	5.74	7.5	6.9	118978	12612
2016	11	30	1:00	3.2	-0.5	-0.4	7.2	18	-0.05	5.82	7.5	8.6	118979	12612
2016	11	30	4:30	3.1	-0.6	-0.5	3.5	5	-0.06	5.75	7.5	7.0	118980	12612
2016	11	30	7:30	3.1	-0.5	-0.5	4.7	7	-0.06	5.68	7.5	12.2	118981	12612
2016	11	30	10:40	3.0	-0.4	-0.4	6.9	28	-0.05	5.59	7.5	10.2	118982	12612
2016	12	3	15:37	2.0	-1.1	-1.1	5.8	8	-0.21	5.22	-8.8	-5.1	119010	12615
2016	12	4	0:18	2.3	-1.4	-1.4	-0.4	-40	-0.22	5.65	-8.7	-0.5	119015	12615
2016	12	4	7:34	2.0	-1.6	-1.6	2.0	-62	-0.26	6.33	-8.8	3.7	119017	12615
2016	12	4	9:50	2.6	-1.8	-1.8	5.9	-53	-0.24	5.81	-8.8	5.0	119018	12615

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2016	12	4	12:50	2.5	-1.6	-1.6	3.0	-46	-0.21	5.99	-8.8	7.1	119019	12615
2016	12	4	15:50	2.4	-1.6	-1.6	4.6	-29	-0.22	5.90	-8.8	8.3	119020	12615
2016	12	6	10:46	2.8	-0.4	-0.5	5.5	50	-0.05	5.92	-8.0	20.4	119028	12615
2016	12	6	13:00	2.1	-0.3	-0.3	0.2	13	-0.05	5.76	-8.0	20.4	119029	12615
2017	1	16	16:30	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-1.5	-26	-0.09	4.64	9.1	-17.6	119358	12626
2017	1	17	4:30	0.7	-0.1	-0.1	-0.9	-19	-0.05	4.30	10.0	-15.2	119362	12626
2017	1	17	7:00	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-1.8	-20	-0.06	4.22	10.0	-13.7	119363	12626
2017	1	17	13:34	2.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.4	-5	-0.02	4.95	6.8	-24.1	119365	12626
2017	1	17	20:02	1.9	-0.1	-0.1	-2.2	-9	-0.01	4.95	6.8	-20.6	119367	12626
2017	1	18	12:54	1.0	-0.0	-0.0	-0.5	-6	-0.01	3.65	2.0	0.8	119377	12626
2017	1	19	2:45	1.8	-0.1	-0.1	0.8	-12	-0.03	4.68	6.8	-3.5	119385	12626
2017	1	19	4:15	1.8	-0.2	-0.2	0.2	-13	-0.05	4.62	6.8	-2.6	119386	12626
2017	1	20	20:01	1.2	-0.1	-0.1	3.6	5	-0.04	4.31	6.6	13.9	119415	12626
2017	1	23	20:30	1.7	0.7	0.7	0.6	40	0.21	4.00	3.9	8.4	119437	12627
2017	1	23	22:00	1.6	0.7	0.7	8.5	74	0.21	4.02	3.9	9.3	119438	12627
2017	1	24	6:13	1.5	0.5	0.5	4.6	46	0.18	3.95	3.9	13.8	119442	12627
2017	1	24	7:30	1.4	0.5	0.5	2.8	51	0.16	4.02	3.9	14.6	119443	12627
2017	1	24	19:05	3.0	-0.7	-0.7	1.2	13	-0.08	5.60	10.3	1.9	119445	12628
2017	1	25	4:29	3.5	-0.5	-0.5	-1.6	-24	-0.05	5.84	10.3	7.4	119448	12628
2017	1	25	7:44	3.6	-0.1	-0.0	0.7	-9	-0.00	5.81	10.3	9.2	119449	12628
2017	1	25	11:00	3.6	0.1	0.1	2.5	-15	0.01	5.71	10.3	8.8	119450	12628
2017	1	25	14:36	3.8	0.4	0.4	1.4	0	0.03	5.63	10.2	8.6	119451	12628
2017	1	25	21:16	3.7	0.7	0.7	0.4	-3	0.06	5.56	10.3	16.7	119453	12628
2017	1	26	0:17	3.7	0.7	0.7	2.1	0	0.06	5.56	10.1	12.8	119454	12628
2017	1	26	3:27	3.3	0.4	0.5	3.5	12	0.05	5.30	10.3	19.9	119455	12628
2017	1	26	8:39	3.3	0.2	0.2	1.6	-4	0.02	5.42	10.4	25.6	119456	12628
2017	1	26	12:04	3.1	0.2	0.2	0.6	0	0.03	5.24	10.4	26.2	119457	12628
2017	1	26	21:52	3.0	0.0	0.0	1.8	0	0.00	5.06	9.8	19.8	119461	12628
2017	1	27	7:44	2.7	-0.0	-0.0	3.0	-1	-0.01	4.93	9.5	19.0	119463	12628
2017	1	27	12:00	2.6	-0.1	-0.1	3.1	-3	-0.02	4.73	9.5	23.0	119464	12628
2017	2	17	18:31	0.7	-0.1	-0.1	-0.6	-24	-0.10	3.44	8.9	-16.3	119622	12636
2017	2	22	6:31	1.9	0.7	0.7	2.5	47	0.15	4.99	15.2	-22.1	119676	12638
2017	2	23	20:40	2.4	0.4	0.4	4.6	40	0.07	5.18	16.6	-15.4	119690	12638

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2017	2	24	1:00	2.4	0.5	0.5	5.3	44	0.08	5.23	17.2	-24.5	119691	12638
2017	2	24	4:15	2.3	0.4	0.3	4.8	49	0.06	5.28	17.2	-22.8	119692	12638
2017	2	24	21:01	2.2	0.3	0.3	2.1	14	0.05	5.45	17.2	-13.5	119697	12638
2017	2	25	0:10	2.2	0.3	0.3	4.4	19	0.05	5.50	17.2	-11.8	119698	12638
2017	2	25	3:15	2.2	0.2	0.2	2.3	10	0.04	5.41	17.2	-10.1	119699	12638
2017	2	25	6:30	2.1	0.2	0.2	2.8	18	0.03	5.43	17.2	-8.3	119700	12638
2017	2	26	7:01	1.6	0.4	0.3	2.0	37	0.09	5.11	17.2	4.0	119710	12638
2017	2	27	6:22	1.6	-0.1	-0.1	1.2	2	-0.02	4.80	17.2	16.8	119715	12638
2017	2	27	22:54	1.6	0.1	0.1	1.9	1	0.02	4.41	17.2	25.9	119717	12638
2017	3	23	23:40	0.5	-0.0	-0.0	-0.1	-6	-0.03	3.05	5.0	-22.2	123174	12643
2017	3	25	0:11	0.6	-0.0	-0.0	0.8	0	-0.02	2.74	5.8	-17.1	123179	12643
2017	3	25	6:35	0.6	-0.0	-0.0	0.5	4	-0.01	2.62	6.0	-15.4	123181	12643
2017	3	30	5:00	2.4	-0.5	-0.5	0.7	-18	-0.07	5.44	-11.0	-15.3	123215	12645
2017	3	30	6:37	2.4	-0.6	-0.6	0.4	-28	-0.09	5.46	-10.9	-16.1	123216	12645
2017	3	30	20:02	2.9	-0.1	-0.1	3.1	18	-0.01	6.15	-11.4	-20.2	123242	12645
2017	3	31	1:00	3.3	-0.2	-0.2	4.8	14	-0.02	5.96	-11.4	-17.4	123243	12645
2017	3	31	19:18	5.9	1.9	1.9	13.4	102	0.11	5.64	-11.5	-7.2	123248	12645
2017	4	1	4:30	6.3	1.5	1.5	5.5	21	0.08	5.94	-11.5	-2.1	123249	12645
2017	4	1	6:14	6.2	1.6	1.6	8.0	22	0.09	5.96	-11.5	-1.1	123250	12645
2017	4	1	9:00	6.5	1.7	1.7	14.3	103	0.09	5.99	-11.4	0.4	123251	12645
2017	4	1	11:00	5.8	0.8	0.9	9.0	7	0.05	5.96	-10.8	1.9	123252	12645
2017	4	1	19:22	5.7	-0.0	-0.1	12.8	82	-0.00	6.05	-10.8	5.0	123256	12645
2017	4	2	8:03	6.5	2.0	1.9	12.9	200	0.12	5.22	-10.9	10.5	123259	12645
2017	4	3	10:05	6.3	3.7	3.5	5.3	385	0.19	6.19	-9.3	16.6	123266	12645
2017	4	20	19:21	2.6	0.8	0.8	4.7	92	0.13	4.93	8.8	-22.4	123393	12651
2017	4	21	8:00	2.6	0.7	0.7	0.9	43	0.12	4.98	9.4	-25.0	123397	12651
2017	4	21	21:30	2.6	0.6	0.6	-0.1	36	0.09	4.96	9.6	-18.4	123402	12651
2017	4	22	7:00	2.7	0.8	0.8	4.8	59	0.13	4.61	9.8	-19.5	123405	12651
2017	4	22	10:49	2.8	0.8	0.8	5.1	76	0.12	4.87	9.5	-26.0	123406	12651
2017	4	22	12:20	2.9	0.8	0.8	2.5	59	0.12	5.13	9.5	-25.1	123407	12651
2017	4	22	17:04	3.0	1.1	1.1	2.2	50	0.14	5.18	9.5	-22.5	123409	12651
2017	4	23	10:45	2.6	0.6	0.5	2.7	48	0.09	4.89	9.4	-12.4	123411	12651
2017	4	23	12:14	2.8	0.6	0.6	0.1	25	0.09	5.05	9.4	-11.6	123412	12651

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2017	4	23	19:05	2.9	0.7	0.6	3.1	48	0.09	5.00	9.4	-7.7	123415	12651
2017	4	23	20:53	2.9	0.7	0.7	3.2	51	0.10	4.93	9.4	-6.8	123416	12651
2017	4	23	22:28	2.7	0.6	0.6	4.2	63	0.09	4.95	9.4	-5.9	123417	12651
2017	4	24	16:34	2.4	0.4	0.4	1.4	18	0.07	4.65	9.3	4.2	123422	12651
2017	4	24	19:50	2.4	0.4	0.4	2.8	22	0.07	4.63	9.3	6.0	123423	12651
2017	4	24	23:03	2.3	0.4	0.4	2.3	15	0.08	4.62	9.3	7.7	123424	12651
2017	4	25	2:03	2.2	0.4	0.4	2.0	17	0.08	4.67	9.3	9.4	123425	12651
2017	4	25	10:25	2.0	0.3	0.3	0.4	21	0.07	4.73	9.8	13.0	123427	12651
2017	4	25	11:55	2.1	0.3	0.3	-1.0	9	0.06	4.64	9.8	13.8	123428	12651
2017	4	25	13:25	2.0	0.3	0.3	-0.8	6	0.06	4.64	9.8	14.6	123429	12651
2017	4	25	19:04	2.0	0.2	0.2	1.9	13	0.05	4.69	9.8	17.8	123434	12651
2017	4	25	20:34	2.0	0.3	0.3	1.9	20	0.06	4.67	9.8	18.6	123435	12651
2017	4	25	22:04	2.0	0.2	0.2	1.7	15	0.05	4.65	9.8	19.4	123436	12651
2017	4	25	23:34	1.9	0.2	0.2	1.9	20	0.05	4.69	9.6	10.4	123437	12651
2017	4	26	1:04	1.9	0.2	0.2	1.3	19	0.05	4.70	9.8	21.1	123438	12651
2017	4	26	2:36	2.0	0.2	0.2	2.1	21	0.05	4.58	9.8	21.9	123439	12651
2017	4	26	6:14	1.9	0.3	0.2	3.4	35	0.06	4.69	9.8	24.0	123442	12651
2017	4	26	7:44	1.9	0.1	0.1	2.7	13	0.03	4.61	9.8	24.8	123443	12651
2017	4	26	9:14	1.9	0.2	0.2	1.3	13	0.04	4.62	9.8	25.6	123444	12651
2017	4	26	10:44	1.7	0.1	0.1	1.4	23	0.04	4.56	9.8	26.5	123445	12651
2017	4	26	12:14	1.8	0.1	0.1	1.4	17	0.03	4.62	9.8	26.7	123446	12651
2017	4	26	19:44	1.6	0.1	0.1	1.2	11	0.02	4.59	9.3	16.8	123449	12651
2017	4	27	0:14	1.6	0.0	0.0	1.1	7	0.00	4.65	9.1	16.6	123452	12651
2017	4	29	12:46	1.4	0.1	0.1	2.0	23	0.04	3.14	-11.0	12.3	123468	12653
2017	4	29	19:32	0.9	-0.0	-0.0	0.6	2	-0.01	3.39	-11.1	14.7	123471	12653
2017	4	30	6:45	0.8	-0.0	-0.0	-0.0	0	-0.00	3.08	-11.2	18.9	123473	12653
2017	5	4	16:04	1.1	0.2	0.2	2.8	22	0.07	4.18	9.9	18.2	123494	12654
2017	5	4	23:55	2.1	0.3	0.3	3.8	45	0.07	4.46	9.7	14.3	123496	12654
2017	5	5	8:03	1.5	0.2	0.2	3.3	35	0.08	4.14	9.9	27.1	123498	12654
2017	5	5	19:52	1.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	9	0.09	3.85	10.3	19.2	123502	12654
2017	5	6	10:23	0.8	-0.1	-0.1	-1.6	-7	-0.05	3.68	11.6	-21.0	123504	12655
2017	5	20	10:26	0.7	0.1	0.1	-0.4	10	0.10	2.65	10.3	-20.7	123646	12656
2017	5	20	12:08	0.7	0.1	0.1	-0.7	5	0.05	2.70	10.3	-15.3	123647	12656

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2017	5	20	13:45	0.7	0.1	0.1	1.2	11	0.09	2.77	10.3	-19.0	123648	12656
2017	5	20	18:41	0.6	0.1	0.1	0.8	6	0.11	2.85	10.3	-16.3	123651	12656
2017	5	21	1:15	0.6	0.1	0.1	-1.5	4	0.08	2.84	10.3	-6.3	123652	12656
2017	5	21	4:30	0.6	0.1	0.0	1.1	7	0.05	2.87	10.3	-9.9	123653	12656
2017	5	21	11:05	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5	12	0.10	2.89	10.3	-7.2	123655	12656
2017	5	23	11:07	0.8	0.1	0.1	2.4	16	0.08	3.17	11.8	-5.7	123670	12659
2017	5	23	20:32	0.9	0.1	0.1	0.3	0	0.07	3.13	11.8	-0.5	123677	12659
2017	5	25	10:09	2.2	0.4	0.4	3.3	43	0.08	4.48	11.7	13.7	123691	12659
2017	5	25	23:17	2.8	0.6	0.6	3.1	46	0.09	4.48	11.8	27.7	123698	12659
2017	5	26	9:07	1.7	0.7	0.7	7.1	70	0.19	4.26	11.6	17.0	123746	12659
2017	6	4	1:23	2.6	1.8	1.8	0.9	120	0.33	4.21	4.0	-21.1	123762	12661
2017	6	5	0:31	2.5	1.9	1.7	-0.8	146	0.33	4.51	4.0	-15.4	123770	12661
2017	6	5	15:11	2.4	1.8	1.7	4.2	134	0.32	4.73	4.1	-22.7	123775	12661
2017	6	5	18:30	2.5	1.8	1.7	2.4	97	0.30	4.78	4.1	-20.8	123776	12661
2017	6	5	21:40	2.5	1.6	1.5	2.6	88	0.27	4.68	4.1	-19.1	123777	12661
2017	6	6	4:10	2.2	1.1	1.1	0.2	60	0.22	4.74	4.1	-15.4	123779	12661
2017	6	6	15:50	2.0	0.6	0.6	2.7	56	0.13	4.60	4.1	-9.2	123783	12661
2017	6	6	20:36	1.9	0.4	0.4	2.7	34	0.09	4.62	4.1	-6.2	123784	12661
2017	6	16	22:10	1.2	0.4	0.4	2.4	26	0.15	4.99	8.5	-16.2	123878	12662
2017	6	17	2:20	1.2	0.5	0.5	1.2	23	0.15	4.96	8.5	-14.3	123880	12662
2017	6	17	2:50	1.2	0.4	0.4	1.0	23	0.15	5.01	8.4	-28.6	123881	12662
2017	6	17	13:56	1.1	0.4	0.4	-0.1	26	0.15	4.67	8.4	-22.5	123885	12662
2017	6	17	14:26	1.2	0.4	0.4	0.8	24	0.14	5.03	8.4	-22.2	123886	12662
2017	6	18	1:25	1.2	0.4	0.4	0.7	22	0.14	4.71	8.4	-16.1	123890	12662
2017	6	18	1:55	1.3	0.4	0.4	0.2	20	0.13	4.94	8.4	-15.8	123891	12662
2017	6	18	3:03	1.3	0.5	0.5	0.4	24	0.14	4.90	8.4	-15.2	123892	12662
2017	6	18	9:36	1.4	0.4	0.4	0.9	29	0.13	4.81	8.4	-6.7	123895	12662
2017	6	18	11:15	1.4	0.4	0.4	2.1	30	0.13	4.78	8.4	-10.7	123896	12662
2017	6	19	6:56	1.2	0.5	0.5	1.8	32	0.18	4.33	8.4	-0.8	123900	12662
2017	6	21	0:00	0.9	0.2	0.2	2.1	21	0.10	4.25	8.4	23.1	123914	12662
2017	6	21	1:40	0.9	0.3	0.3	1.1	18	0.14	4.31	8.4	24.0	123915	12662
2017	6	21	3:20	0.9	0.3	0.3	1.0	20	0.15	4.22	8.4	24.9	123916	12662
2017	6	21	4:50	0.9	0.3	0.3	0.8	16	0.16	4.17	8.3	15.4	123917	12662

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (continued)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2017	6	21	8:10	0.9	0.3	0.3	0.6	21	0.16	4.06	8.6	13.8	123918	12662
2017	6	21	19:35	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.7	17	0.12	3.94	8.6	16.9	123924	12662
2017	7	9	17:15	12.2	-6.6	-6.5	10.7	-95	-0.15	7.30	-9.1	-19.5	124042	12665
2017	7	9	20:31	9.3	-6.0	-6.0	9.9	1	-0.17	7.72	-9.1	-13.1	124043	12665
2017	7	9	23:38	12.9	-7.9	-7.9	19.9	9	-0.16	7.56	-9.4	-24.9	124044	12665
2017	7	10	2:54	11.0	-7.0	-7.0	24.3	131	-0.18	6.96	-9.4	-23.1	124045	12665
2017	7	10	12:45	12.4	-6.1	-6.2	33.0	263	-0.14	6.88	-9.4	-17.7	124048	12665
2017	7	10	16:13	10.7	-5.5	-5.6	29.5	217	-0.15	6.76	-9.4	-15.8	124049	12665
2017	7	10	19:27	10.0	-4.3	-4.4	30.3	220	-0.13	6.60	-9.3	-9.2	124050	12665
2017	7	10	22:40	11.8	-8.8	-8.9	10.3	-28	-0.18	8.25	-9.4	-12.2	124051	12665
2017	7	11	1:51	11.6	-8.6	-8.6	6.9	-53	-0.18	8.19	-9.4	-10.4	124052	12665
2017	7	11	5:08	4.4	-4.2	-4.2	2.6	-78	-0.30	6.28	-9.4	-11.9	124053	12665
2017	7	11	11:43	9.1	-9.7	-9.7	2.1	-116	-0.25	8.61	-9.3	-4.8	124054	12665
2017	7	11	13:31	7.5	-6.5	-6.5	3.9	-34	-0.20	8.88	-9.4	-0.7	124055	12665
2017	7	11	15:02	8.6	-9.1	-9.1	-2.3	-121	-0.24	8.88	-9.4	-3.0	124056	12665
2017	7	11	21:37	8.6	-9.1	-9.1	4.7	-61	-0.24	8.86	-9.4	0.7	124060	12665
2017	7	12	2:36	8.3	-7.7	-7.7	2.2	-69	-0.21	8.76	-9.4	3.4	124063	12665
2017	7	12	7:22	8.2	-7.0	-7.0	7.3	-33	-0.19	8.85	-9.4	6.0	124064	12665
2017	7	12	10:40	7.4	-5.3	-5.3	7.3	-1	-0.16	8.95	-9.4	9.1	124065	12665
2017	7	12	19:01	7.6	-5.5	-5.4	0.7	-65	-0.16	8.94	-9.4	12.5	124068	12665
2017	7	13	1:24	6.8	-6.6	-6.6	3.6	-41	-0.22	8.67	-9.4	16.0	124069	12665
2017	7	13	7:57	7.2	-8.9	-8.9	-2.2	-102	-0.27	9.19	-9.4	19.6	124070	12665
2017	7	13	14:35	7.3	-8.5	-8.5	9.2	0	-0.26	8.87	-9.4	23.3	124071	12665
2017	7	13	19:31	7.0	-8.9	-8.9	-0.1	-64	-0.29	8.88	-9.4	26.0	124074	12665
2017	7	14	13:33	6.4	-10.2	-10.2	-1.2	-123	-0.37	8.60	-8.7	18.2	124079	12665
2017	8	4	2:47	3.0	0.1	0.1	1.9	45	0.02	5.01	-7.9	-23.1	124241	12670
2017	8	4	7:45	2.9	0.2	0.2	-0.8	39	0.03	5.09	-8.3	-26.2	124242	12670
2017	8	9	2:54	2.8	0.4	0.4	3.3	42	0.05	6.12	-9.6	19.7	124288	12670
2017	8	9	4:21	2.9	0.5	0.4	1.5	34	0.05	6.09	-9.6	20.5	124289	12670
2017	8	11	2:04	1.6	0.1	0.1	0.2	15	0.02	5.64	-8.3	28.2	124304	12670
2017	8	17	12:30	3.9	-1.6	-1.6	5.1	-19	-0.18	4.69	8.6	-25.1	124356	12671
2017	8	19	8:31	3.1	0.6	0.5	6.3	65	0.09	4.48	7.6	-14.9	124386	12671
2017	8	22	8:26	3.3	-0.8	-0.8	2.9	10	-0.09	5.32	10.5	14.6	124395	12671

Table 5 continued

Table 5 (*continued*)

y	m	d	h:m	e_M	h_M	h_M^{LS}	h_M^{SS}	$\mathcal{H}_C$	r_M	ℓ_M	λ	$\mathcal{L}$	MapID	AR
2017	8	24	17:00	3.2	0.8	0.8	1.4	34	0.09	5.61	4.6	-26.1	124411	12672
2017	8	24	21:30	4.0	0.7	0.7	9.7	118	0.07	5.47	5.0	-14.7	124414	12672
2017	8	25	3:50	3.3	1.1	1.1	2.6	50	0.12	5.71	4.6	-20.0	124416	12672
2017	8	25	7:05	2.8	0.6	0.6	-0.9	26	0.08	5.20	4.9	-9.9	124417	12672
2017	8	25	10:15	2.5	0.5	0.5	2.4	28	0.08	4.78	4.8	-8.3	124418	12672
2017	8	25	14:10	2.5	0.5	0.5	1.7	27	0.09	4.76	4.6	-14.3	124419	12672
2017	8	25	18:56	3.3	0.9	0.9	15.8	187	0.12	4.86	4.6	-11.7	124421	12672
2017	8	25	22:15	3.6	0.9	0.8	10.9	146	0.10	5.01	4.6	-9.2	124422	12672
2017	8	26	2:40	3.3	0.6	0.6	4.0	55	0.07	4.95	4.6	-7.3	124423	12672
2017	8	26	18:05	2.6	0.3	0.3	2.8	37	0.05	4.68	6.3	-2.5	124429	12672
2017	9	5	3:04	11.9	3.6	3.5	13.1	105	0.07	8.41	9.6	5.9	124491	12674
2017	9	5	10:51	15.6	-23.6	-22.5	-15.8	-1193	-0.52	5.80	-8.8	20.8	124494	12673
2017	9	5	14:00	15.3	-23.7	-22.6	15.1	-1049	-0.53	5.81	-8.4	13.0	124495	12673
2017	9	5	16:00	15.2	-22.7	-21.6	-5.2	-1294	-0.52	5.75	-8.8	23.6	124496	12673
2017	9	5	18:09	15.6	-23.5	-22.2	-13.4	-1451	-0.52	5.77	-8.8	24.8	124499	12673
2017	9	6	0:02	15.5	-20.3	-18.9	-18.8	-1503	-0.47	5.57	-8.8	28.3	124501	12673
2017	9	6	6:14	13.5	-14.3	-12.9	-21.4	-1268	-0.39	5.35	-8.0	17.1	124502	12673
2017	9	7	0:01	9.4	-11.9	-11.3	1.6	-687	-0.44	5.70	-7.5	22.5	124514	12673
2017	9	30	5:16	3.6	-0.6	-0.6	2.6	-5	-0.05	5.77	-10.9	-6.5	124655	12682